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METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D3.1

Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)

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Terms and abbreviations

BCP	Border Control Point
CNIL	Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés (French Data Protection Authority)
DoA	Description of Action
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EES	Entry/Exit System
ENISA	European Union Agency for Network and Information Security
ETIAS	European Travel Information and Authorization System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SBC	Smart Border Control
WP29	Article 29 Working Party

Executive Summary

This document is Deliverable D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)” of WP3 of the METICOS project.

The aim of this document is to complete a comprehensive Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) of the METICOS platform. A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. In other words, a DPIA is a process for building and demonstrating compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other privacy requirements.

To achieve its purposes, this Deliverable:

- details why a DPIA is required in the context of METICOS, identifies the elements that a DPIA must contain in accordance with the GDPR and describes the methodology being followed to conduct the DPIA of the METICOS platform.
- contains an overview of the processing carried out by the METICOS platform, a description of the data collected by each data source, a data flow diagram and an overall description of processes being carried out by each component.
- ensures that the METICOS platform is built in compliance with the following privacy principles: purpose limitation, lawfulness, necessity of the data processing operations, data minimization, data quality and storage limitation. Controls protecting data subjects’ rights as well as the legal exemptions are also being examined.
- proceeds to the identification of the risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects and contains recommendations of technical or operational solutions and mitigation measures to address those risks.

The analysis and hence the outcomes of this Deliverable will in turn inform the METICOS developers and data providers about the ways for developing and using the METICOS technology to ensure that data protection and privacy principles are taken care of.

It is important to note that, in line with the Grant Agreement, this Deliverable (D3.1) is due on M12 and consists into a first version of the DPIA. This first version is based on the information having been provided by the partners at this stage (M12) of the project where some technical aspects are still to be defined or detailed. Moreover, during the project duration, the development of the METICOS platform might evolve and deviate from the way it is currently being described in this document. Therefore, the second final version of the DPIA (D3.6), which is due on M26, will contain the necessary updates and reviews on the elements that are still unknown or insufficiently detailed in this first version. Moreover, in order to ensure completeness and consistency, the final version (D3.6) of the DPIA will also contain the views of external stakeholders (e.g., technical experts, lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, citizens, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, as well as others) and of the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) of the METICOS joint controllers as well as the opinion of the Ethical Advisory Board.

1 Introduction

1.1 General description of METICOS

The efficient processing of an ever-increasing number of travellers at EU borders calls for more flexible, automated and scalable “no-gate” border security solutions. A “No-Gate Border Crossing Point Solution” is understood to be “a method which enables travellers to cross borders without being slowed down by physical checks, based on automated risk-assessment and/or biometric verification processes”¹. Recent regulatory efforts made by the EU in the context of the “Smart Borders initiative” are meant to frame no-gate border solutions. With this regard, during METICOS’ life cycle (2020-2023), a number of key transformations are planned to take place. Among these, two new systems are expected to have a big impact on the border crossing experience: the Entry/Exit System (EES)², with planned entry into operation in the first quarter of 2022, and the European Travel Information and Authorization System (ETIAS)³, planned to be operational by the end 2022.

Concretely, “no gate solutions” – which play an important role in the automation of the clearance process of travellers during security border control – include, amongst others, “airport mobile apps, self-service kiosk check-ins, smart boarding gates, and self-service baggage drop, tagging and tracking, along with biometric technologies”⁴. According to the European Commission, “one main challenge is to manage the flow of travellers and goods arriving at our external borders, while at the same time tackling irregular migration and enhancing our internal security. Any novel technology or organisational measure will need to be accepted by the European citizens”⁵.

In this context, METICOS aims to introduce tools and methods being used in the field of Big Data Analysis in the context of border management to evaluate the user’s acceptance and the efficiency of modern control technologies of EU borders such as “no gate solutions”. It is therefore positioned as “an initiative to create a real-time decision-support system with regard to different Smart Border

¹ S. BINDER et al. “Biometric technology in “no-gate border crossing solutions” under consideration of privacy, ethical, regulatory and social acceptance.” In *Multimedia tools and applications*, 2020, pp. 1-14.

² The Entry/Exit System (EES) will be an automated IT system for registering travelers from third-countries, both short-stay visa holders and visa exempt travelers, each time they cross an EU external border. The system will register the person's name, type of the travel document, biometric data (fingerprints and captured facial images) and the date and place of entry and exit. It will also record refusals of entry. EES will replace the current system of manual stamping of passports, which is time consuming, does not provide reliable data on border crossings and does not allow a systematic detection of over-stayers (travelers who have exceeded the maximum duration of their authorized stay).

³ ETIAS will be a largely automated IT system created to identify security, irregular migration or high epidemic risks posed by visa-exempt visitors travelling to the Schengen States, whilst at the same time facilitate crossing borders for the vast majority of travellers who do not pose such risks. Non-EU nationals who do not need a visa to travel to the Schengen area will have to apply for a travel authorisation through the ETIAS system prior to their trip. The ETIAS travel authorisation will be a mandatory pre-condition for entry to the Schengen States. It will be checked together with the travel documents by the border guards when crossing the EU border. This prior verification of visa exempt non-EU citizens will facilitate border checks; avoid bureaucracy and delays for travellers when presenting themselves at the borders; ensure a coordinated and harmonised risk assessment of third-country nationals; and substantially reduce the number of refusals of entry at border crossing points.

⁴ PERSONA, “D2.1: A study of latest and new generation no-gate crossing point solutions”, p. 17, available at

⁵ H2020 call “SU-BES01-2018-2019-2020”.

control technologies that empowers three major stakeholder groups within the European border control sector (i.e., travellers and border control authorities & service providers) to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency. To this end, the METICOS project develops a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and users' acceptance of border control technologies. The proposed platform will provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions"⁶.

METICOS will be demonstrated in pilot implementations involving informed and consenting participants playing the role of travellers and border control staff. Only adults (persons over 18 years of age) having the capacity to consent will be recruited for the purpose of the METICOS pilots. More detailed information about the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants can be found in D1.1 – “H – Requirement No. 2”.

1.2 Document objective and scope

As the methods and technologies being used in METICOS stem from the field of “Big Data Analysis”, there are obviously important privacy and data protection requirements that need to be seriously taken into account. The term “Big Data” usually identifies extremely large data sets that may be analysed computationally to extract inferences about data patterns, trends, and correlations⁷. The Gartner IT glossary defines it as follows: “Big data is high-volume, high-velocity and high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information processing for enhanced insight and decision making”⁸. Given the nature of Big Data and its uses, the Council of Europe considers that “the application of some of the traditional principles of data processing (e.g. the principle of data minimisation, purpose limitation, fairness and transparency, and free, specific and informed consent) may be challenging”⁹.

More concretely, according to the Article 29 Working Party, Big Data raises concerns about:

- “the sheer scale of data collection, tracking and profiling, also taking into account the variety and detail of the data collected and the fact that data are often combined from many different sources;
- the security of data, with levels of protection shown to be lagging behind the expansion in volume;
- transparency: unless they are provided with sufficient information, individuals will be subject to decisions that they do not understand and have no control over;
- inaccuracy, discrimination, exclusion and economic imbalance; and

⁶ METICOS's Description of Action, p. 2.

⁷ Council of Europe, Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of Big Data, Strasbourg, 23 January 2017, p. 2, available at <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=09000016806ebe7a>

⁸ Gartner IT glossary Big data. <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/big-data>

⁹ Council of Europe, Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of Big Data, Strasbourg, 23 January 2017, p. 1

- increased possibilities of government surveillance”¹⁰.

Bearing these challenges in mind, the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) believes that “the question is not whether to apply data protection law to big data, but rather how to apply it innovatively in new environments. Our current data protection principles, including transparency, proportionality and purpose limitation, provide the base line we will need to protect more dynamically our fundamental rights in the world of big data. They must, however, be complemented by ‘new’ principles which have developed over the years such as accountability and privacy by design and by default”¹¹. Therefore, in the context of Big Data, good and accountable practices require to conduct a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) prior to the processing to ensure data protection by design and by default.

The objective of this document is to conduct a comprehensive DPIA of the METICOS platform. It aims to identify and mitigate the ethical and privacy risks as well as to help prevent negative impacts of the METICOS platform on individuals’ privacy and data protection rights. The analysis and hence the outcomes of this deliverable (D3.1) will in turn inform the METICOS developers (including all partners) about the ways to develop and use the METICOS technology so that data protection and privacy principles are taken care of.

It is important to highlight that this document constitutes a first version (D3.1) of the METICOS DPIA which is based on the progress of the project at M12. Hence, its scope is limited to the development aspects which are already known. Further updates and assessments of the pilots will be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

1.3 Relation with other deliverables

Although this Deliverable (D3.1) is a standalone document, it is strongly interconnected with several other METICOS deliverables.

- Deliverable D1.1 describes the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants during METICOS project lifetime. This document also contains templates of information sheet and consent forms to ensure voluntary participation.
- Deliverable D1.3 identifies the Data Protection Officer (DPO) per partner (where applicable) or contains of detailed data protection policy for partners which are not required to appoint a DPO. In addition, D1.3 describes in a general manner the risks deriving from personal data processing operations in research. Findings of this first part are then applied to the METICOS project circumstances in the second part. Finally, part three examines the need for conducting a DPIA within the METICOS project and concludes that such DPIA will be carried out in T3.2.
- Deliverable D1.4 presents the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorized access to personal data or the equipment used for processing of METICOS data. Also, in this deliverable the technical and organizational measures that will be implemented

¹⁰ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation, adopted on 2 April 2013, WP203, p.45.

¹¹ EDPS, Opinion 7/2015, Meeting the challenges of big data - A call for transparency, user control, data protection by design and accountability, p.3, 19 November 2015, available at https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/15-11-19_big_data_en.pdf

to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants are analyzed along with the anonymization/pseudonymization techniques.

- Deliverable D1.8 establishes an independent Ethical Board to monitor the ethics issues in the METICOS project and how they are handled. The members of the Ethical Board may raise any ethical or legal issue related to the METICOS project and must be consulted at least on the ethics issues raised in the ethics screening report. Amongst these, the Ethical Board is competent for personal data protection issues in the context of the piloting and validation phase, including data collected from social media.
- Deliverable D3.3 seeks to incorporate human rights as a fundamental axis of evaluating the METICOS system, and in turn prevent METICOS components from breaching fundamental rights and contributing to re-creating gender discrimination and/or negatively impacting socio-cultural factors. This Deliverable also aims to understand what the socio, cultural and gender impact is within the context of METICOS.

1.4 Document structure

The structure of this document is as follows:

- Section 1 provides for an introductory description of the document containing its objectives, its scope, its relations with other Deliverables and its structure.
- Section 2 recalls the aim of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), details why a DPIA is required in the context of METICOS, identifies the elements that a DPIA must contain in accordance with the GDPR, and finally describes the methodology being followed to conduct the DPIA of the METICOS platform.
- Section 3 contains an overview of the processing carried out by the METICOS platform, a description of the data collected by each data source, a data flow diagram and an overall description of processes being carried out by each component.
- Section 4 ensures that the METICOS platform is built in compliance with the following privacy principles: purpose limitation, lawfulness, necessity of the data processing operations, data minimization, data quality and storage limitation. This section also describes the planned controls protecting data subjects' rights as well as the legal exemptions being applied.
- Section 5 identifies the risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects and formulates recommendations, technical or operational solutions and mitigation measures to address those risks.
- Section 6 provides for a general conclusion.

2 Methodological approach

2.1 Concept of data protection impact assessment (DPIA)

The European authorities always supported the inclusion of a “risk-based approach” in the EU data protection legal framework.¹² In consistence with this risk-based approach, article 35 of the General Data Protection regulation¹³ (GDPR) introduces the concept of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). A DPIA is “a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR. In other words, a DPIA is a process for building and demonstrating compliance.”¹⁴

Conducting a DPIA and documenting the outcomes is an important method to demonstrate that privacy is being taken seriously in METICOS. It evidences the commitment of the consortium to accountability --a core principle and requirement under the GDPR.

2.2 DPIA required for the METICOS system

Carrying out a DPIA is not mandatory for every processing operation. A DPIA is only required when the processing is “likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons”. However, the notion of “high risk” is not defined in the GDPR.

The GDPR provides three non-exhaustive examples of processing operations which are likely to result in an inherent high risk¹⁵:

- (i) a systematic¹⁶ and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling¹⁷, and on which decisions are

¹² Article 29 Working party, Statement on the role of a risk-based approach in data protection legal frameworks, WP 218, adopted on 30 May 2014.

¹³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

¹⁴ See Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP 248 rev.01, adopted on 4 April 2017, last revised and adopted on 4 October 2017

¹⁵ General Data Protection Regulation, art. 35.3.

¹⁶ The Article 29 Working Party interprets ‘systematic’ as “meaning one or more of the following: occurring according to a system; pre-arranged, organised or methodical; taking place as part of a general plan for data collection; carried out as part of a strategy”. See Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP248 rev.01 (4 October 2017), p. 10.

¹⁷ According to article 4(4) of the General Data Protection Regulation, “profiling means any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyze or predict aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behavior, location or movements”.

- based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person;
- (ii) processing on a large scale¹⁸ of special categories of data¹⁹ or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences²⁰; or
- (iii) a systematic monitoring²¹ of a publicly accessible area²² on a large scale.

In order to ensure a consistent interpretation of the circumstances in which a DPIA is mandatory, the Article 29 Working Party issued guidelines to clarify this notion and provide criteria to help identify the circumstances in which a DPIA is needed²³.

The table below lists each criterion listed by the Article 29 Working Party, indicates whether each criterion applies to the METICOS platform and provides for a short explanation.

Criterion identified by WP29	Applicability	Explanation
Evaluation or scoring, including profiling and predicting, especially from “aspects concerning the data subject's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements”.	Yes	Some components of the METICOS platform will classify users in categories based on several factors (e.g. level of acceptance, complexity level of technology used, support available for using technology, flexibility in using technology).
Automated decision making with legal or similar significant effect: processing that aims at taking decisions on data subjects producing “legal effects	No	The METICOS platform will not perform any automated decision making nor any processing having

¹⁸ The Article 29 Working Party recommends that the following factors, in particular, be considered when determining whether the processing is carried out on a large scale: “the number of data subjects concerned either as a specific number or as a proportion of the relevant population; the volume of data and/or the range of different data items being processed; the duration, or permanence, of the data processing activity; the geographical extent of the processing activity”. See Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Officers (‘DPOs’), WP243 rev.01 (5 April 2017), p. 9.

¹⁹ As referred to in article 9.1 of the General Data Protection Regulation.

²⁰ As referred to in article 10 of the General Data Protection Regulation.

²¹ According to the Article 29 Working Party, “the concept of ‘monitoring of the behaviour of data subjects’ is mentioned in recital 24 and clearly includes all forms of tracking and profiling on the internet, including for the purposes of behavioural advertising. However, the notion of monitoring is not restricted to the online environment and online tracking should only be considered as one example of monitoring the behaviour of data subjects”. See Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Officers (‘DPOs’), WP243 rev.01 (5 April 2017), p. 8.

²² The Article 29 Working Party interprets “publicly accessible area” as being “any place open to any member of the public, for example a piazza, a shopping centre, a street, a market place, a train station or a public library”. See Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP248 rev.01 (4 October 2017), p.9.

²³ Ibid, pp. 9-11.

<p>concerning the natural person” or which “similarly significantly affects the natural person”.</p>		<p>substantial consequences on individual travelers/border guards. Indeed, the purpose of the METICOS platform is to provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers; not to perform a risk-based assessment per traveler.</p>
<p>Systematic monitoring: processing used to observe, monitor or control data subjects, including data collected through networks or “a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area”.</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>According to the Article 29 Working Party, data collected through networks is collected on a publicly accessible area²⁴. In the context of METICOS, the Big Data Analytics component retrieves any tweets publicly posted about Smart Border Control Technologies to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.</p>
<p>Sensitive data or data of a highly personal nature: this includes special categories of personal data as defined in Article 9 (for example information about individuals’ political opinions), as well as personal data relating to criminal convictions or offences as defined in Article 10. Beyond these provisions of the GDPR, some categories of data can be considered as increasing the possible risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals. These personal data are considered as sensitive (as this term is commonly understood) because they are linked to household and private activities (such as electronic communications whose confidentiality should be protected), or because they impact the exercise of a fundamental right (such as location data whose collection questions the freedom of movement) or because their violation clearly involves serious impacts in the data subject’s daily life (such as financial data that might be used for payment fraud).</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>The Article 29 Working Party considers that personal data which are linked to household and private activities such as electronic communications are sensitive as this term is commonly understood. In the context of METICOS, the Big Data Analytics component retrieves any tweets publicly posted about Smart Border Control Technologies to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.</p>
<p>Data processed on a large scale: the GDPR does not define what constitutes large-scale, though recital 91 provides some guidance. In any event, the WP29</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>In real-world conditions, the aim of the METICOS platform is to process data on a large scale.</p>

²⁴ Ibid., p.9.

<p>recommends that the following factors, in particular, be considered when determining whether the processing is carried out on a large scale:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) the number of data subjects concerned, either as a specific number or as a proportion of the relevant population; b) the volume of data and/or the range of different data items being processed; c) the duration, or permanence, of the data processing activity; d) the geographical extent of the processing activity. 		
<p>Matching or combining datasets, for example originating from two or more data processing operations performed for different purposes and/or by different data controllers in a way that would exceed the reasonable expectations of the data subject.</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>The METICOS platform processes data acquired from various heterogeneous sources. Primary data (collected directly from data subjects) originate from the METICOS mobile and tablet applications, social media and questionnaires. Secondary data (existing data that are going to be further processed by METICOS' components) consist of anonymized data originating from border crossing points and personal data from social media.</p>
<p>Data concerning vulnerable data subjects (recital 75): the processing of this type of data is a criterion because of the increased power imbalance between the data subjects and the data controller, meaning the individuals may be unable to easily consent to, or oppose, the processing of their data, or exercise their rights. Vulnerable data subjects may include children (they can be considered as not able to knowingly and thoughtfully oppose or consent to the processing of their data), employees, more vulnerable segments of the population requiring special protection (mentally ill persons, asylum seekers, or the elderly, patients, etc.), and in any case where an imbalance in the relationship between the position of the data subject and the controller can be identified.</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>The METICOS platform might potentially process data about vulnerable data subjects such as elderly, people with disabilities, asylum seekers, etc.</p>

<p>Innovative use or applying new technological or organisational solutions: The GDPR makes it clear (Article 35(1) and recitals 89 and 91) that the use of a new technology, defined in “accordance with the achieved state of technological knowledge” (recital 91), can trigger the need to carry out a DPIA. This is because the use of such technology can involve novel forms of data collection and usage, possibly with a high risk to individuals’ rights and freedoms. Indeed, the personal and social consequences of the deployment of a new technology may be unknown.</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>The METICOS platform aims to measure user’s acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies by using methods and tools used in the field of Big Data Analysis. Applying Big Data tools and methodologies in the field of acceptance of border control technologies is considered as innovative.</p>
<p>When the processing in itself “prevents data subjects from exercising a right or using a service or a contract” This includes processing operations that aims at allowing, modifying or refusing data subjects’ access to a service or entry into a contract.</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Elderly and people with disabilities might potentially be unable to participate to the METICOS platform.</p>

In most cases, the Article 29 Working Party considers that a processing meeting two criteria would require a DPIA to be carried out. Moreover, the Working Party considers that “the more criteria are met by the processing, the more likely it is to present a high risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects, and therefore to require a DPIA, regardless of the measures which the controller envisages to adopt”²⁵.

In the context of METICOS, given that the envisaged processing meets 8 of the 9 criteria identified by the Article 29 Working Party, it is being considered that this processing “is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons”. By consequence, a DPIA is required prior to such processing.

2.3 Content of the DPIA

The GDPR sets out the minimum features of a DPIA (Article 35(7), and recitals 84 and 90):

1. “a description of the envisaged processing operations and the purposes of the processing”;
2. “an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing”;
3. “an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects”;
4. “the measures envisaged to:
 - a) “address the risks”;
 - b) “demonstrate compliance with [the GDPR]”.

²⁵ Ibid., p. 11.

In addition, the controller must also seek the advice of the Data Protection Officer(s) (DPOs) when designated²⁶ and “seek the views of data subjects or their representatives”²⁷. According to the Article 29 Working Party, “those views could be sought through a variety of means, depending on the context (e.g. a generic study related to the purpose and means of the processing operation, a question to the staff representatives, or usual surveys sent to the data controller’s future customers) ensuring that the controller has a lawful basis for processing any personal data involved in seeking such views”²⁸. It is also “recommended to seek the advice from independent experts of different professions (lawyers, IT experts, security experts, sociologists, ethics, etc.)”²⁹.

The figure hereunder of the Article 29 Working Party illustrates the generic iterative process for carrying out a DPIA.

Figure 1- Process for carrying out a DPIA³⁰

It should be underlined that the process depicted is iterative: in practice, each of the stages is revisited multiple times before the DPIA can be completed. This is the case of METICOS: in line with the

²⁶ Article 35, §2 of the GDPR.

²⁷ Article 35, §9 of the GDPR.

²⁸ Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP248 rev.01 (4 October 2017), p.15.

²⁹ Recommendations for a privacy impact assessment framework for the European Union, Deliverable D3: http://www.piafproject.eu/ref/PIAF_D3_final.pdf.

³⁰ This figure originates from Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP248 rev.01 (4 October 2017), p.16.

Description of Action, this Deliverable (D3.1) constitutes a first version of the DPIA. A second final version (D3.6) will be submitted on M26. By consequence:

- The aforementioned steps 1 to 4 will be carried out in this Deliverable taking into account the information available on M12 of the METICOS project. As the full scope of the data processing is still subject to updates and modifications, this first version of the DPIA should be considered as an interim version that will be updated and, if necessary corrected, in D3.6.
- In this first version of the DPIA, it was not feasible yet to seek the views of data subjects or their representatives. This step will be completed in D3.6 in accordance with the Description of Action (DoA) which requires that the impact assessment will “consult with relevant project stakeholders and external stakeholders (e.g., technical experts, lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, citizens, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, as well as others) to validate the analysis and suggest additional issues for consideration”. The DoA also requires to “hold a virtual workshop to validate findings”. This will be carried out by gathering the opinion of the Ethical Advisory Board on the DPIA process.
- In this first version of the DPIA, it was not feasible to already seek the advice of each partner’s DPOs. This step will be completed in D3.6. As a reminder the DPO of each partner’s organization has been identified in D1.3 (“POPD-Requirement No.5”).

2.4 Criteria for an acceptable DPIA methodology

The GDPR provides flexibility to determine the precise structure and form of the DPIA to allow for this to fit with existing working practices. Different methodologies could be used to assist in the implementation of the basic requirements set out in the GDPR. In order to allow these different approaches to exist, common criteria have been identified by the Article 29 Working Party.³¹ The criteria listed in the figure 2 below can be used to show that a particular DPIA methodology meets the standards required by the GDPR.

³¹ Ibid., p.22.

- a systematic description of the processing is provided (Article 35(7)(a)):
 - nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing are taken into account (recital 90);
 - personal data, recipients and period for which the personal data will be stored are recorded;
 - a functional description of the processing operation is provided;
 - the assets on which personal data rely (hardware, software, networks, people, paper or paper transmission channels) are identified;
 - compliance with approved codes of conduct is taken into account (Article 35(8));
- necessity and proportionality are assessed (Article 35(7)(b)):
 - measures envisaged to comply with the Regulation are determined (Article 35(7)(d) and recital 90), taking into account:
 - measures contributing to the proportionality and the necessity of the processing on the basis of:
 - specified, explicit and legitimate purpose(s) (Article 5(1)(b));
 - lawfulness of processing (Article 6);
 - adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary data (Article 5(1)(c));
 - limited storage duration (Article 5(1)(e));
 - measures contributing to the rights of the data subjects:
 - information provided to the data subject (Articles 12, 13 and 14);
 - right of access and to data portability (Articles 15 and 20);
 - right to rectification and to erasure (Articles 16, 17 and 19);
 - right to object and to restriction of processing (Article 18, 19 and 21);
 - relationships with processors (Article 28);
 - safeguards surrounding international transfer(s) (Chapter V);
 - prior consultation (Article 36).
- risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects are managed (Article 35(7)(c)):
 - origin, nature, particularity and severity of the risks are appreciated (cf. recital 84) or, more specifically, for each risk (illegitimate access, undesired modification, and disappearance of data) from the perspective of the data subjects:
 - risks sources are taken into account (recital 90);
 - potential impacts to the rights and freedoms of data subjects are identified in case of events including illegitimate access, undesired modification and disappearance of data;
 - threats that could lead to illegitimate access, undesired modification and disappearance of data are identified;
 - likelihood and severity are estimated (recital 90);
 - measures envisaged to treat those risks are determined (Article 35(7)(d) and recital 90);
- interested parties are involved:
 - the advice of the DPO is sought (Article 35(2));
 - the views of data subjects or their representatives are sought, where appropriate (Article 35(9)).

Figure 2 - Criteria for an acceptable DPIA methodology

2.5 Choice of a methodology for METICOS

On November 2017, the French Data Protection Authority (CNIL) released on its website an open source ready to use software tool for DPIAs, which can be downloaded for free.³² In February 2018, to assist in this process and take into account all GDPR requirements, CNIL has updated its “PIA Guides”

³² See <https://www.cnil.fr/en/open-source-pia-software-helps-carry-out-data-protection-impact-assesment>

as well as its DPIA tool.³³ The method describes how to use the EBIOS³⁴ method in the specific context of "Personal Data Protection". This methodology is consistent with the Article 29 Working Party's Guidelines and with risk management international standards.

CNIL's DPIA method is composed of three guides:

- The method explains how to carry out a DPIA;
- The models help to formalize a DPIA by detailing how to handle the different sections introduced in the method;
- The knowledge base is a code of practice that lists measures to be used to treat the risks.

Figure 3 - CNIL's DPIA methodology

Given the broad recognition of CNIL's fulfilment in the field of protection of personal data as well as the fact that the CNIL's DPIA tool is open source and that is well documented, it was decided to base METICOS' DPIA on this methodology. However, some sections of METICOS' DPIA are more detailed than what is required by the CNIL methodology. The reason is that METICOS's DPIA also was inspired by the work carried out in the H2020 PERSONA project³⁵.

³³ See <https://www.cnil.fr/en/cnil-publishes-update-its-pia-guides>

³⁴ EBIOS – Expression des Besoins et Identification des Objectifs de Sécurité (Expression of Needs and Identification of Security Objectives) – is the name of the risk management methodology published by the Agence Nationale de la Sécurité des Systèmes d'Information (ANSSI/French National Cybersecurity Agency).

³⁵ PERSONA (Privacy, ethical, regulatory and social no-gate crossing point solutions acceptance) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grand agreement 787123. The project's main goal was to design and establish an integrated impact assessment method (IAM PERSONA) to appropriately evaluate the impacts of no-gate crossing point solutions, taking into account social acceptance, ethical and legal requirements, to ensure that these technologies meet the expectations of public authorities and travellers.

3 Systematic description of the data processing

3.1 Overview of the processing

This section should:

- Present a brief outline of the product under consideration, its nature, scope, context, purposes and stakes
- Identify the data controller and any processors.
- List the references applicable to the processing, which are necessary or must be complied with, not least the approved codes of conduct.

3.1.1 Purpose of the processing

Article 5, §1, (a) of the GDPR imposes that personal data must be collected for specified purposes and not be further processed in a manner that is incompatible with that purpose. According to the Article 29 Working Party, “Purpose specification is an essential condition to processing personal data and a prerequisite for applying other data quality requirements. Purpose specification and the concept of compatible use contribute to transparency, legal certainty and predictability; they aim to protect the data subject by setting limits on how controllers are able to use their data and reinforce the fairness of the processing. The limitation should, for example, prevent the use of individuals’ personal data in a way (or for further purposes) that they might find unexpected, inappropriate or otherwise objectionable”³⁶.

By consequence, purpose specification requires an internal assessment and is a necessary condition for accountability. It is a key first step to ensure compliance with applicable data protection law.

The table 1 hereunder describes the processing under consideration in this DPIA.

Table 1 - Description of the processing under consideration

	Description of the processing under consideration
Name of the initiative under assessment	METICOS platform
Description of the processing	The METICOS platform is a set of components which aim to measure user’s acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies by using methods and tools used in the field of Big Data Analysis.
Processing purposes	The purpose of the METICOS platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort

³⁶ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation, adopted on 2 April 2013, WP 203, p.11.

	expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.
Processing stakes³⁷	The processing stakes of the METICOS platform is to create a decision-support system with regard to different Smart Border control technologies in order to empower three major stakeholder groups within the European border control sector (travellers, border control authorities & service providers) to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency.

Unlike the TRESPASS project³⁸, it is important to emphasize that the METICOS project does not aim to develop a risk-based border management solution. By consequence, the purpose of the METICOS platform is not to adjust the number and types of security checks required for each traveller neither to perform any kind of risk-based screening leading to individual consequences for travellers willing to cross border crossing points.

3.1.2 Identification of the data controller(s) and processor(s)

The concepts of controller, joint controller and processor play a crucial role in the application of data protection law, since they determine who shall be responsible for compliance with different data protection rules, and how data subjects can exercise their rights in practice. The concepts of controller, joint controller and processor are functional concepts in that they aim to allocate responsibilities according to the actual roles of the parties and autonomous concepts in the sense that they should be interpreted mainly according to EU data protection law. These concepts are defined as follows:

- Article 4(7) of the GDPR defined the controller as « the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data »;
- Article 4(8) of the GDPR defines the processor as « the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller ».

These concepts are further detailed in the European Data Protection Board’s Guidelines 07/2020³⁹, as summarised hereunder:

³⁷ The CNIL template details that “processing stakes” answers the question “What are the expected benefits (for the organization, for the data subjects, for society in general, etc.)?”, See CNIL, Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA), Application to IoT devices, February 2018, p. 2., available at

<https://www.cnil.fr/sites/default/files/atoms/files/cnil-pia-piaf-connectedobjects-en.pdf>

³⁸ TRESPASS (robust Risk based Screening and alert System for PASsengers and luggage) is a H2020 project funded under grant agreement No 787120. See <https://www.tresspass.eu/The-project>

³⁹ EDPB, Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, adopted on 02 September 2020, available at

https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/consultation/edpb_guidelines_202007_controllerprocessor_en.pdf

- **Controller:** In principle, there is no limitation as to the type of entity that may assume the role of a controller but in practice it is usually the organisation as such, and not an individual within the organisation (such as the CEO, an employee or a member of the board), that acts as a controller. A controller is a body that decides certain key elements of the processing. Controllership may be defined by law or may stem from an analysis of the factual elements or circumstances of the case. Certain processing activities can be seen as naturally attached to the role of an entity. In many cases, the terms of a contract can help identify the controller, although they are not decisive in all circumstances. A controller determines the purposes and means of the processing, i.e. the why and how of the processing. The controller must decide on both purposes and means. However, some more practical aspects of implementation (“non-essential means”) can be left to the processor. It is not necessary that the controller actually has access to the data that is being processed to be qualified as a controller.
- **Joint controllers:** The qualification as joint controllers may arise where more than one actor is involved in the processing. The GDPR introduces specific rules for joint controllers and sets a framework to govern their relationship. The overarching criterion for joint controllership to exist is the joint participation of two or more entities in the determination of the purposes and means of a processing operation. Joint participation can take the form of a common decision taken by two or more entities or result from converging decisions by two or more entities, where the decisions complement each other and are necessary for the processing to take place in such a manner that they have a tangible impact on the determination of the purposes and means of the processing. An important criterion is that the processing would not be possible without both parties’ participation in the sense that the processing by each party is inseparable, i.e. inextricably linked. The joint participation needs to include the determination of purposes on the one hand and the determination of means on the other hand.
- **Processor:** A processor is a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, which processes personal data on behalf of the controller. Two basic conditions for qualifying as processor exist: that it is a separate entity in relation to the controller and that it processes personal data on the controller’s behalf. The processor must not process the data otherwise than according to the controller’s instructions. The controller’s instructions may still leave a certain degree of discretion about how to best serve the controller’s interests, allowing the processor to choose the most suitable technical and organisational means. A processor infringes the GDPR, however, if it goes beyond the controller’s instructions and starts to determine its own purposes and means of the processing. The processor will then be considered a controller in respect of that processing and may be subject to sanctions for going beyond the controller’s instructions.

The table 2 hereunder aims to identify the data controllers and the data processors of the METICOS platform both during the project activities (including the pilots) and after the project activities, in real-world conditions, should the outcome of the METICOS platform be used after the project’s end.

Table 2 - Identification of the controller(s) and processor(s)

Identification of the data controller(s) and the data processor(s)		
	During the project/pilots	In real-world conditions should the outcome of the METICOS platform be used after the project’s end.
Data controller(s)	During the project’s duration, for research purposes, including the pilots, the joint data controllers of the METICOS platform are the partners of the METICOS consortium which are developing the different components/technologies. These are: EUC, MAGG, NTNU, ICCS, JOAFG, NetU, SIMAVI and AIT.	In real-world conditions, the data controller of the METICOS platform is not identified. This depends on the actual implementation of the platform after the project’s end.
Data processor(s)	<p>No data processor is identified at this stage. At this stage of the project, it is envisaged to store the data processed by the METICOS platform on METICOS’s servers.</p> <p>Potentially, at a later stage of the project, the use of an external Cloud solution may be examined. In this event, the identification of the data processor (the Cloud provider) will be carried out.</p>	This depends on the actual implementation of the platform after the project’s end.

3.1.3 Identification of specific guidelines/recommendations applicable to the processing

The aim of this section is to list the references applicable to the processing which are necessary or must be complied with. The table 3 below lists important European guidelines and recommendations to be taken into account when assessing the respect of privacy principles by Big Data analytics tools.

Table 3 - Specific guidelines/recommendations applicable to the processing

Specific guidelines/recommendations applicable to the processing	Description
Guidelines of the Council of Europe on the protection of individuals with regard to the	The Guidelines recommend measures that Parties, controllers and processors should take to prevent the potential negative impact of the use of Big Data on human dignity, human rights, and fundamental individual and collective freedoms, in particular with regard to personal data protection.

<p>processing of personal data in a world of big data⁴⁰</p>	
<p>Statement on Statement of the WP29 on the impact of the development of big data on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of their personal data in the EU⁴¹</p>	<p>The data protection authorities of the European Union, represented in the Article 29 Working Party (WP29), consider that the development of big data technologies can have important consequences on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of their personal data in the EU. The Working Party has decided to publish this statement to communicate a number of key messages on this issue.</p>
<p>Opinion 7/2015 of the EDPS: Meeting the challenges of big data - A call for transparency, user control, data protection by design and accountability⁴²</p>	<p>This Opinion follows on from the EDPS’s previous Opinion on Digital Ethics. It addresses the challenge of data protection to “go digital” - the first objective of the EDPS Strategy – “customizing existing data protection principles to fit the global digital arena”, also in the light of the EU’s plans for the Digital Single Market. It is consistent with the approach of the Article 29 Working Party on data protection aspects of the use of new technologies, such as the ‘Internet of Things’, to which the EDPS contributed as a full member of the group.</p>
<p>ENISA, Privacy by design in big data - An overview of privacy enhancing technologies in the era of big data analytics⁴³</p>	<p>In this study, ENISA first explains the need to shift the discussion from “big data versus privacy” to “big data with privacy”, adopting the privacy and data protection principles as an essential value of big data, not only for the benefit of the individuals, but also for the very prosperity of big data analytics. In this respect, the concept of privacy by design is key in identifying the privacy requirements early at the big data analytics value chain and in subsequently implementing the necessary technical and organizational measures. Therefore, after an analysis of the proposed privacy by design strategies in the different phases of the big data value chain, ENISA provides an overview of specific identified privacy enhancing technologies that are of special interest for the current and future big data landscape. In particular, anonymization, the “traditional” analytics technique, the emerging area of encrypted search and</p>

⁴⁰ Council of Europe, Consultative Committee of the Convention for the protection of individuals with regard to automatic processing of personal data (T-PD), Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of Big Data, T-PD(2017)01, Strasbourg, 23 January 2017.

⁴¹ Article 29 Working Party, Statement on Statement of the WP29 on the impact of the development of big data on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of their personal data in the EU, WP 221, adopted on 16 September 2014.

⁴² EDPS, Meeting the challenges of big data - A call for transparency, user control, data protection by design and accountability, 19 November 2015.

⁴³ ENISA, Privacy by design in big data - An overview of privacy enhancing technologies in the era of big data analytics, December 2015.

	<p>privacy preserving computations, granular access control mechanisms, policy enforcement and accountability, as well as data provenance issues are discussed. Moreover, new transparency and access tools in big data are explored, together with techniques for user empowerment and control.</p>
<p>ENISA, Big Data Security - Good Practices and Recommendations on the Security of Big Data Systems⁴⁴</p>	<p>The study aims at identifying the key security challenges that the companies are facing when implementing Big Data solutions, from infrastructures to analytics applications, and how those are mitigated. The analysis focuses on the use of Big Data by private organizations in specific sectors (e.g. Finance, Energy, Telecom). However, more institutions (e.g. research centers, public organizations, and government agencies) have been considered as well.</p>
<p>ENISA, Big Data Threat Landscape and Good Practice Guide⁴⁵</p>	<p>This Threat Landscape and Good Practice Guide for Big Data provides an overview of the current state of security in the Big Data area. In particular, it identifies Big Data assets, analyses exposure of these assets to threats, lists threat agents, takes into account published vulnerabilities and risks, and points to emerging good practices and new research in the field. To this aim, ongoing community-driven efforts and publicly available information have been considered.</p>

It should be noted that no approved codes of conduct (see Art. 40 of the GDPR) nor certifications regarding data protection (see Art. 42 of the GDPR) applicable to Big Data analytics tools were identified.

3.2 Data, processes and supporting assets

The aim of this section is to identify and describe:

- The METICOS data sources;
- The data collected by each data source;
- The examination of the sensitivity of the data being collected;
- Persons with access to the personal data;
- The processes and personal data supporting assets for the entire personal data life cycle (from collection to erasure).

⁴⁴ ENISA, Big Data Security - Good Practices and Recommendations on the Security of Big Data Systems, December 2015.

⁴⁵ ENISA, Big Data Threat Landscape and Good Practice Guide, January 2016.

3.2.1 Identification and description of the METICOS data sources

Given that the purpose of the METICOS platform is to measure the efficiency of border control technologies as well as to evaluate the users' acceptance of such technologies, data concerning two different sets of "users" are being collected:

- a) Data related to travelers;
- b) Data related to border control staff.

The METICOS platform receives data originating from two categories of data sources as shown in Figure 4:

1. Primary Data: Primary data is the type of data that is collected directly from informed and consented "users" during the METICOS project activities and during pilots at the Border Control Points. Such primary data originates from:
 - a. Questionnaires addressing specific questions about border crossing points, their control routines and technologies used;
 - b. Twitter: After crossing the border in the METICOS pilot site, the user is posting a tweet using a specific hashtag (e.g. #METICOS-EU_pilot);
 - c. METICOS Mobile Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a mobile application;
 - d. METICOS Tablet Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a tablet application.
2. Secondary data: Secondary data is the type of data that is relevant to METICOS but has been collected in the past. Such data are already available to use in the context of the project from existing sources. Such secondary data originates from:
 - a. Statistical data originating from border crossing points' databases;
 - b. Twitter: The aim is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.
 - c. Online reviews of BCPs on blogs/websites

The diagram below schematically represents the different data sources of the METICOS platform and regroups these data sources in two categories (primary data and secondary data). It should be noted that this diagram might be subject to changes during the METICOS project. In such case, this diagram will be updated in D3.7 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” due on M26.

Figure 4 – General overview of the METICOS data sources

3.2.2 Identification and description of the data collected by each data source

Having identified and described the data sources of the METICOS platform in the previous section, the aim of this section is to identify and describe the categories of data being collected by each data source.

Before listing the categories of data being collected via each data source, it is important to highlight the following distinction regarding the data being collected:

- As regards primary data collected directly from users via questionnaires, twitter, the METICOS Mobile Application and the METICOS tablet Application as well as secondary data collected via social media, blogs and websites, these data should be considered as personal data in the sense of article 4(1) of the GDPR. This article defines “personal data” as being “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”. In order to comply with the data minimization and security principles, the METICOS platform anonymizes these data before presenting KPIs and metrics to the border control authorities and decision makers. In case, during the progress of the project, it appears that anonymization cannot be applied in METICOS case, since it does not allow the individual components to fulfill their purpose, these data will be pseudonymized by the METICOS platform. Further details about the anonymization processes which are planned to be carried out will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.
- As regards secondary data collected from border crossing points’ databases, the METICOS consortium decided to collect only data that has already undergone a prior anonymization process by the end-user organizations (border control authorities). Recital 26 of the GDPR defines “anonymous information” as being “information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person”. As a reminder, the GDPR does not apply to the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes. However, the GDPR applies to the anonymization process itself. In order to ensure that this anonymization process is carried out effectively by the end-user organizations before that the information is transmitted to the METICOS platform, it is planned to organize a workshop with MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS and CYPOL. This workshop will be dedicated to discuss the anonymization techniques being applied in order to avoid risks of re-identification. These anonymization techniques will be detailed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

Below, tables 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 list and describe the categories of data being collected by each METICOS data source.

Table 4 – Primary data collected by the METICOS Mobile Application

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset title	Description
Primary Data	METICOS Mobile Application	Time to cross the border	Overall time required to cross the border using the SBC technology
		Travelers' demographics & profile	Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Frequent Flyer, Travel Habits/Experience, Level of Education, Sex, Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background/Orientation, Trust in BC Authorities, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence + Current occupation, Current work status [employed-unemployed-self-employed], per traveler or Rank, Work Experience, per staff member
		Staff member demographics & profile	
		Smiley face	After crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, the traveler is pressing a smiley face in order to indicate their satisfaction with the border crossing experience.
		Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes	Including questions regarding speed (queue, waiting time?), accuracy, efficiency, user friendliness, data protection, privacy, ethical perception of traveler for the specific technology (and potentially generally) Moreover, some examples of questions may include: What are the main problems when crossing the border in general and have the SBC managed to resolve some? Which type of biometrics are you more in favor of? What kind of difficulties you encounter when using SBC? How important do you think speed/privacy/data protection/security/trustworthiness is in the context of SBC implementation? Was there sufficient and efficient communication signs? Any impact on personal health/wellbeing? Was there the adequate guidance needed?
		Unstructured data in form of free text questions	Some examples of questions asked may include: In your opinion, the advantages of SBC outweigh the disadvantages and why? What problems have you encountered

			while using SBC technologies? Give a short review of your experience with SBC today. What did you like/not like?
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Table 5 – Primary data collected by the METICOS Tablet Application

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset title	Description
Primary Data	METICOS Tablet Application	Travelers' demographics & profile	Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Frequent Flyer, Travel Habits/Experience, Level of Education, Sex, Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background/Orientation, Trust in BC Authorities, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence
		Staff member demographics & profile	+ Current occupation, Current work status [employed-unemployed-self-employed], per traveler or Rank, Work Experience, per staff member
		Smiley face	After crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, the traveler is pressing a smiley face in order to indicate their satisfaction with the border crossing experience.
		Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes	Including questions regarding speed (queue, waiting time ?), accuracy, efficiency, user friendliness, data protection, privacy, ethical perception of traveler for the specific technology (and potentially generally) Moreover, some examples of questions may include: What are the main problems when crossing the border in general and have the SBC managed to resolve some? Which type of biometrics are you more in favor of? What kind of difficulties you encounter when using SBC? How important do you think speed/privacy/data protection/security/trustworthiness is in the context of SBC implementation? Was there sufficient and efficient communication signs? Any impact on personal health/wellbeing? Was there the adequate guidance needed?

		Unstructured data in form of free text questions	Some examples of questions asked may include: In your opinion, the advantages of SBC outweigh the disadvantages and why? What problems have you encountered while using SBC technologies? Give a short review of your experience with SBC today. What did you like/not like?
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Table 6 – Primary Data collected through Questionnaires

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset title	Description
Primary Data	Questionnaires	Travelers' demographics & profile	Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Frequent Flyer, Level of Education, Sex; Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence, Current occupation, Current work status [employed-unemployed-self-employed], per passenger
		Staff member demographics & profile	Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Level of Education, Sex; Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background/Orientation, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence, Rank, Work Experience, per staff member
		Likert Scale	To indicate general satisfaction of a staff member's experience with a certain Border Control technology/system
		Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes	Including questions regarding speed(queue, waiting time ?), accuracy, efficiency, user friendliness, data protection, privacy, ethical perception of traveler for the specific technology (and potentially generally) Moreover, some examples of questions may include: What are the main problems when crossing the border in general and have the SBC managed to resolve some? Which type of biometrics are you more in favor of? What kind of difficulties you encounter when using SBC? How

			important do you think speed/privacy/data protection/security/trustworthiness is in the context of SBC implementation? Was there sufficient and efficient communication signs? Any impact on personal health/wellbeing? Was there the adequate guidance needed?
		Unstructured data in form of free text questions	Some examples of questions asked may include: In your opinion, the advantages of SBC outweigh the disadvantages and why? What problems have you encountered while using SBC technologies? Give a short review of your experience with SBC today. What did you like/not like?

Table 7 - Primary data processed through Twitter

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset title	Description
Primary Data	Twitter	Tweet after completing use case METICOS pilot	After crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, the traveler is posting a tweet using a dedicated hashtag (e.g. #METICOS-EU_pilot).

Table 8 - Secondary Data processed through Social Media

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset title	Description
Secondary Data	Twitter (and possibly other social media sources)	Tweets (or other) regarding acceptance of Border Control Technologies	Tweets (or other) collected for a long period of time which concern the public and societal acceptance of border control technologies.

Table 9 - Secondary data collected from Blogs/Websites

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset title	Description
Secondary Data	Blogs/Websites	Online reviews of BCPs	Online reviews which concern specific BCPs (airports/ports/land borders).

Table 10 - Secondary data collected from border crossing points

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset title	Description
		Checked passengers per flight/day	Anonymous information regarding passengers that have scanned their boarding passes
		Waiting Time - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/per hour)	Waiting time for passengers using SBC technologies
		Waiting Time - manual control (average per passenger/per hour)	Waiting time for passengers passing through manual security check
		Queue length - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/ per hour)	Length for the queue of passengers using SBC technologies

Secondary Data	Anonymized data from border crossing points	Queue length - manual control (average per passenger/ per hour)	Length for the queue of passengers passing through manual control
		Number of passengers controlled by Border Guard (per month/per hour)	Number of passengers controlled by Border Guard (per month/per hour)
		Number of passengers who used ABC technologies (per month/per hour)	Number of passengers who used ABC technologies (per month/per hour)
		Passenger Demographics & Profiles	Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Frequent Flyer, Level of Education, Familiarity with Technology, Sex per passenger as a timeseries. Also if following data is available: Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence, Current occupation, Current work status[employed-unemployed-self-employed],), per passenger
		Recurring travelers per origin/destination	Estimate distribution of travelers doing multiple trips to the same destination (frequency/duration/...)
		Historical passenger data	Number of passengers per trip (source to destination) over multiple years, allowing to infer seasonality patterns on the various routes
		Number of access attempts with documents not accepted by the system - For BCP technologies	Number of access attempts which have failed because the documents were not accepted by the system (measured daily/per month)
		Number of access attempts with non-eligible documents - For BCP technologies	Number of access attempts which have failed because the documents were not eligible (measured daily/per month)

		Number of access attempts with valid e-passport but biometric verification error - For BCP technologies	Number of access attempts which have failed because there was a biometric error (measured daily/per month)
		Number of complaints regarding SBC technologies (by date)	Number of complaints filed regarding problems with the use of SBC technologies (as a timeseries)
		Downtime of system per month/year - For BCP technologies	Total amount of time when the system and/or the SBC technology components are not operational
		FAR / FRR - For BCP technologies	False Accept Rate / False Reject Rate
		Total verification time - For BCP technologies	This is defined as the time needed to fully verify an eligible traveler, regardless of the outcome of each particular check (document authentication, biometric verification, background checks, etc.)
		Total access time - For BCP technologies	This is defined as the total time spent in the process by an eligible traveler since the first interaction with the system (i.e. presentation of the travel document in an integrated two-step process ABC system, entry in the mantrap space in a one step process ABC system, first interaction with the verification modules in a single eGate or segregated two-step process solution).
		Total time of biometric and document verification - For BCP technologies	This is defined as the individual time needed to verify the biometric/ document process
Information from airline companies	Flight delays	Flight delays/cancellations (as a timeseries)	

3.2.3 Life cycle of data and processes

This section aims to present and describe how the METICOS system generally works, with a diagram of data flows.

Due to the project timeline and the early development of METICOS platform, it should be highlighted that the life cycle of data and processes of the METICOS platform presented in this Deliverable might still be subject to changes. In case of changes or modifications in the next period of the project, these will be presented and taken into account in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

The table 11 below explains how the METICOS platform generally works.

Table 11- Life cycle of data and processes

Processes	Description of the process
<p>1. Statistical (anonymous) data are collected from border crossing points databases.</p>	<p>(Secondary) Statistical and anonymous data listed in table 10 are collected from the databases of end-user organizations (border control crossing points). These statistical data are coming, either from static files (e.g. PPA) or APIs (e.g. Hellenic Police). These statistical data are being processed by the “Universal connector” and by the “Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems”⁴⁶ in order to ensure uniform access to the various data sources based on authentication/authorization schemes and on profile-privileges and user rights. APIs will be created to store and retrieve these data which will be accessible through the METICOS middleware.</p>
<p>2. Personal data are collected from Twitter (and possibly other social media sources) as well as on Blogs/Websites.</p>	<p>(Secondary) Public tweets (and possibly data originating from other social media sources⁴⁷) as well as online reviews on Blogs/Websites regarding acceptance of border control technologies by travelers are collected. The goal is to derive the sentiments that people have towards border control.</p>
<p>3. Personal data are collected directly from travelers and border control staff.</p>	<p>(Primary) Personal data are collected directly from users via the METICOS Mobile Application (see table 4), the METICOS tablet Application (see table 5), questionnaires (see table 6) and Twitter (see</p>

⁴⁶ The Interface with Border Management Information Systems is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing statistical data that BPCs make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservices that offer information like queue lengths, average waiting times, late flights, etc and sends the data agreed with the BPC. It is important to note that the METICOS platform will not be connected with border information system like VIS, SIS or alike.

⁴⁷ In case data originating from other social media sources than twitter are being collected during the project, this will be described and examined in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

	table 7). It should be highlighted that all primary data are collected on the basis of the consent of informed volunteers.
4. The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 & 3 are forwarded to the METICOS middleware.	The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 and 3 are sent to the METICOS middleware which is a software module for integration and information management of heterogeneous data sources.
5. In parallel with step 4, the data collected in steps 1, 2 & 3 are stored in the Data Integration Module.	The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 and 3 are stored in the Data Integration Module. At this stage of the project, it is envisaged to store the data processed by the METICOS platform on METICOS’s servers. Potentially, at a later stage of the project, the use of an external Cloud solution may be examined. In this event, the identification of the data processor (the Cloud provider) and the GDPR compliance of this solution will be carried out in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.
6. The data originating from steps 4 & 5 are being processed by the Big Data Analytics Engine.	The data originating from the METICOS middleware which are stored in the Data Integration Module are sent to the Big Data Analytics Engine. The Big Data Analytics Engine is composed of several sub-components: the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module, the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module and the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module. The general aim of the Big Data Analytics Engine is to uncover hidden patterns amongst attributes of gathered data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.
7. The data originating from step 6 are sent to the Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module.	The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travelers, border authorities).
8. The data originating from steps 6 & 7 are sent to the Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA).	The aim of the Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA) is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyze correlations of data generated from other METICOS components as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies.
9. The data originating from steps 6 & 7 are sent to the Social Toolkit Module.	The social sensing tool is a technology acceptance prediction system for border control technologies. The social sensing tool will analyze and estimate the activity and interactions between migrants/travelers,

	border staffs and border control technologies for technology acceptance prediction.
10. The data originating from steps 8 & 9 are sent to the Personnel Front-End.	After the authorized border control personnel logs in to the system, the Dashboard screen is displayed. Its purpose is to display an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. Some of those metrics might include star ratings over time, speed, ease of use, emotional response. They will be displayed using graphs, pie charts and histograms that span a certain time period that may be selected by the user. The user will also have the ability to view analytics for specific checkpoints as well as aggregated analytics for all checkpoints.

The Data Flow Diagram below schematically illustrates how the METICOS platform generally works

Figure 5 - METICOS' data flow diagram

3.2.4 Overall description of processes being carried out

Table 12 lists in detail all the data processing operations intended to be carried out by each component of the METICOS platform.

Table 12 - Overall description of processes being carried out by each component

Component name	Responsible partner	Description of the process
Universal Connector	SIMAVI	The component offers a uniform access to various data sources. It offers a standard API to access data from different data sources and hides their technological implementation details. The component has multiple connector modules that support various connection types.
Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems Module	NET-U	The Interface with Border Management Information Systems is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing statistical data that BPCs make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservices that offer information like queue lengths, average waiting times, late flights, etc and sends the data agreed with the BPC. The exact manner in which the statistical data will be collected / integrated in the METICOS platform will be detailed in D3.6. It is important to note that the METICOS platform will not be connected with border information system like VIS, SIS or alike.
METICOS Middleware Module	MAGG	All information coming from the data sources (primary and secondary data) will be sent to the middleware module for processing and/or storage. That information will be used to perform data mining and analytics about the passengers' perception of the technologies used at border checkpoints.
Data Integration Module	SIMAVI	METICOS Common Data Management Engine (CDME) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way. All the exchanged information will be translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all METICOS components use them.
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for	ICCS	The Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data will analyse structured data coming from several sources (historical data, real-time data gathered at pilot sites, questionnaires ...). The ADME component at the end of the project will uncover hidden

Structured Data Module		patterns amongst attributes of gathered structured data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module	ICCS	The aim of the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module is to gather and analyse unstructured data from different sources (historical unstructured data, real-time unstructured, data gathered at pilot sites, free text in questionnaires, tweets and social media). Hence, the engine will be capable of extracting data from social media (twitter, reviews, blogs...) in a real-time automated way and storing it with the aim of further processing the data. The engine will include the functionality of sentiment detection (polarity and subjectivity), topic modelling, aspect identification, context detection (most important words, clustering) of social media data (twitter, reviews, blogs, etc.) in order to capture the general acceptance and social acceptance of SBC technologies. The user will be able to see most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that people are tweeting about regarding smart border control technologies, including others.
Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module	ICCS	The purpose of the Cross-Sectorial Big Data Analysis (CS-BDA) Mechanisms module is to infer the acceptance of a BCP or technology by aggregating and analysing data from different sources, locations and formats. It accepts the outputs of other components (ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data, and others). The output of the CS-BDA component will be fed in the DTVA component.
Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA)	ICCS	The aim of Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA) is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyse correlations of data generated from other METICOS components as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies. It will provide a platform where the outputs from the ADME for Structured Data, ADME for Unstructured Data and CS-BDA modules will be visualised and presented.
Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module	AIT	The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travelers, border authorities).
Social Toolkit Module	NTNU	The social sensing tool is a technology acceptance prediction system for border control technologies. The social sensing tool will analyze and estimate the activity and interactions between migrants/travelers, border staffs and border control technologies for

		<p>technology acceptance prediction. The Social Toolkit Module is composed of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The socio-cultural framework; • Automated tools for assessing threshold <p>The socio-cultural framework module (SCFM) will allow the METICOS platform to assess the main reasons behind underlying circumstances that can affect the process of individuals with different sociocultural backgrounds trying to pass through given BCP technologies. It will make use of multiple parameters, such as age, gender, social status, education, professional status, cultural background, lifestyle, native language, gestures etc.</p> <p>The Automated Threshold Assessment Module (ATHAM) will define a specific threshold for each BCP technology when dealing with non-EU travellers. It will include parameters related to the overall complexity of the device/technology used, the level of interaction with different users, response time, the level of flexibility, level of support from border authorities etc., along with context-based data to adjust the threshold accordingly.</p>
<p>Personnel Front-End</p>	<p>MAGG</p>	<p>After the authorized border control personnel logs in to the system, the Dashboard screen is displayed. Its purpose is to display an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. Some of those metrics might include star ratings over time, speed, ease of use, emotional response. They will be displayed using graphs, pie charts and histograms that span a certain time period that may be selected by the user. The user will also have the ability to view analytics for specific checkpoints as well as aggregated analytics for all checkpoints.</p>

3.2.5 Data supporting assets, storage duration and persons having access to the data

Below you will find a table listing in detail the data supporting assets, the storage duration and persons having access to the data.

Table 13 - Data supporting assets and storage duration

IT systems on which the data rely	Storage duration	Persons with access to the personal data
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Questionnaires	To be defined	Researchers of the METICOS joint controllers' organizations
METICOS Mobile Application	To be defined	Researchers of the METICOS joint controllers' organizations
METICOS Tablet Application	To be defined	Researchers of the METICOS joint controllers' organizations
METICOS servers (Data Integration Module)	To be defined	Researchers of the METICOS joint controllers' organizations
End-user Front-End	Will only display anonymous information (dashboards with metrics and KPIs). No storage duration limit is imposed by law.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers of the METICOS joint controllers' organizations • Border control staff, • Decision makers.

At this stage of the project, several important technical aspects still need to be defined or detailed:

- The technical architecture of the Questionnaires, the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications, the METICOS servers and the End-user Front-End still need to be defined. Further detailed information about the technological aspects of the IT systems on which the data rely will be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.
- The storage duration of the data processed by the METICOS platform has not been defined yet. At the latest, it is envisaged to delete the collected personal data at the end of the project' lifetime but this needs to be confirmed. In any case, and the storage duration will be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

4 Assessment of necessity and proportionality

The overall objective of this section is to ensure that the system is built in compliance with privacy principles.

4.1 Controls guaranteeing the proportionality and necessity of the processing

The aim of this sub-section is to:

- Explain and justify that the purpose(s) of the METICOS platform is (are) specified, explicit and legitimate (see Art. 5.1 (b) of the GDPR);
- Explain and justify the necessity of the processing carried out by each component of the METICOS platform;
- Explain and justify the choices made for the METICOS platform to comply with the following requirements:
 1. basis: lawfulness of processing, prohibition of misuse (see Art. 6 of the GDPR);
 2. data minimisation: adequate, relevant and limited (see Art. 5 (c) of the GDPR);
 3. management of sensitive data (art. 9 and 10 of the GDPR);
 4. quality of data: accurate and kept up-to-date (see Art. 5 (d) of the GDPR);
 5. storage periods: limited (see Art. 5 (e) of the GDPR).
- Check that improving the way in which each point is planned, clarified and justified, pursuant to the GDPR, is either not necessary or not possible.
- Where applicable, review their description or propose additional controls.

4.1.1 Justification of the purposes of the METICOS platform

According to Article 5.1 (b) of the GDPR, personal data must be “collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes [...] (‘purpose limitation’)”. The respect of this principle implies:

- Firstly, a clear determination of the purpose for which the personal data are collected and processed. The controller must therefore carefully consider what purpose(s) the personal data will be used;
- Secondly, the purposes must not only be specified in the minds of the persons responsible for data collection. They must also be made explicit. In other words, they must be clearly revealed, explained or expressed in some intelligible form;
- Thirdly, the purposes must be in accordance with all provisions of applicable data protection law, as well as other applicable laws. In other words, “the requirement of legitimacy means that the purposes must be 'in accordance with the law' in the broadest sense. This includes all forms of written and common law, primary and secondary legislation, municipal decrees,

judicial precedents, constitutional principles, fundamental rights, other legal principles, as well as jurisprudence, as such 'law' would be interpreted and taken into account by competent courts”⁴⁸.

Table 14 setting out in detail the foreseen data processing purposes of the METICOS platform and justifying their legitimacy⁴⁹.

Table 14 - Explanation and justification of purposes

Purposes	Legitimacy
<p>The purpose of the METICOS platform is to conduct scientific research.</p>	<p>According to recital 159 of the GDPR: “For the purposes of this Regulation, the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes should be interpreted in a broad manner including for example technological development and demonstration, fundamental research, applied research and privately funded research”. The former Article 29 Working-Party has already pointed out that the term may not be stretched beyond its common meaning though and understands that “scientific research” in this context means “a research project set up in accordance with relevant sector-related methodological and ethical standards, in conformity with good practice”⁵⁰.</p>
<p>The purpose of the METICOS platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.</p>	<p>There is no legal ground forbidding the METICOS joint controllers to measure border control technologies acceptance and efficiency in order to provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers.</p>

⁴⁸ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation, WP 203, p.20

⁴⁹ On the legitimacy of the purpose, see opinion WP 203 of the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party - http://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2013/wp203_en.pdf

⁵⁰ See the Guidelines on Consent under Regulation 2016/679 of the former Article 29 Working-Party from 10.04.2018, WP259 rev.01, 17EN, p. 27 (endorsed by the EDPB).

<p>The purpose of the METICOS platform is NOT to develop a risk-based border management solution. By consequence, the purpose of the METICOS platform is not to adjust the number and types of security checks required for each traveler neither to perform any kind of risk-based screening or profiling leading to individual consequences for travelers willing to cross border crossing points.</p>	<p>Article 8 of the Schengen Border Code lists the checks which may be carried out by border guards at external borders. This list does not foresee the possibility to perform risk-based screening or profiling of travelers on the basis of their acceptance of border control technologies. Hence, the METICOS platform should strictly avoid to share individualized acceptance measurements with border control staff and decision makers.</p>
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From the determination of the purpose of the METICOS platform, it is concluded that no personal data allowing risk-based screening or individualized profiling should be visible via the End-user Front-End to border control staff or decision makers. The End-user Front-End should only be permitted to provide aggregated (anonymous) metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers.

After the end of the METICOS project, should the METICOS platform be used in real world conditions, it is strongly recommended not to allow any border control authority to act as data controller of the METICOS platform. This recommendation is being provided in order to avoid “function-creep”. Function creep “is a risk for data subjects, as it may result in unanticipated use of personal data by the controller or by third parties and in loss of data subject control”. This means that data used for statistical purposes or other research purposes via the METICOS platform should not be available to support measures or decisions that are taken with regard to the individual data subjects concerned.

4.1.2 Explanation of the necessity of the processing carried out by each component

The “necessity” requirement derives from article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights according to which there shall be no interference with the right to privacy except if in accordance with the law and when necessary in a democratic society in the interests of a legitimate purpose. Hence, there is a clear connection between the assessment of necessity and compliance with the purpose limitation principle.

The European Court of Justice considered that “necessity” is a concept which has its own independent meaning in Community law⁵¹. In an early and leading Article 8 case, the Court clarified that “necessary” in this context does not have the flexibility of such expressions as “useful”, “reasonable”, or “desirable” but implies the existence of a “pressing social need” for the interference in question⁵².

Applied to the METICOS platform, this requirement imposes to assess whether the data processing operations carried out by each component can be justified.

⁵¹ Judgment of the European Court of Justice of 16 December 2008 in case C-524/06 (Heinz Huber v Bundesrepublik Deutschland), para 52.

⁵² Judgment of the European Court of Human Rights in case Silver & Others v United Kingdom of 25 March 1983, para 97.

According to the DoA, this step should have been included in T3.3 – “METICOS Ethical, Social and Human Rights Impact Assessment”. However, as the “necessity test” is an explicit requirement of a DPIA, it was decided to include this step in T3.2 – “METICOS Data protection and Privacy Impact Assessment”. In order to ensure consistency with the DoA, this section will be referred to in D3.2 – “Human rights impact assessment (first version)” and in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”.

In order to have an overview of the necessity of the processing carried out by each component of the METICOS system, a questionnaire has been sent to METICOS’ technology providers with the aim to understand :

1. What is being addressed by these components?
2. Why are these components being considered as a solution to these issues?

The table 15 below contains the answers of the METICOS’ technology providers to the following questions:

- Component name
- Responsible partner
- Concrete problem justifying the development of the component
- Causes and consequences of the problem justifying the development of the component
- Likelihood that the problem will persist without intervention
- Why is the component being considered as a solution to this problem?
- Did you consider other alternatives to solve the problem?

Table 15 - Necessity of each component

Component name	Responsible partner	Concrete problem justifying the development of the component	Causes and consequences of the problem justifying the development of the component	Likelihood that the problem will persist without intervention	Why is the component being considered as a solution to this problem?	Did you consider other alternatives to solve the problem?
Universal Connector	SIMAVI	METICOS will integrate with various data sources with different formats. The problem is the distributed nature of this data and the diversity of data formats. The data should be centralized and the format standardized in order to minimize work at component level in order to access and convert the data.	The causes are the heterogenous nature of the infrastructure at BCP level. The consequences are increased effort to access and used the data.	Very likely	It hides the implementation details of the various data sources	No
Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems Module	NET-U	The Interface with Border Management Information Systems is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing statistical data that BPCs make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservice that offer information like queue	Information stored at the national level is considered to be heterogeneous, and thus impossible to combine, aggregate, measure or report upon without first performing the required processing to streamline into agreed data structures. Accordingly, specific and documented	Since different mechanisms are required to provide the integration endpoints and perform the necessary data translations, it is impossible to resolve this problem without the de-facto industry standard of data exchange. Thus, the	Since different mechanisms are required to provide the integration endpoints and perform the necessary data translations, it is impossible to resolve this problem without the de-facto industry standard of data exchange.	No

		lengths, average waiting times, late flights, etc and sends the data agreed with the BPC. It is important to note that the METICOS platform will not be connected with border information system like VIS, SIS or alike	integration endpoints to communicate with the METICOS platform efficiently and effectively.	aforementioned issue will persist in case this component is not implemented.		
METICOS Middleware Module	MAGG	METICOS middleware is a software module for integration and information management of heterogeneous data sources.	The middleware is the "maestro" of the internal information exchange between the components, such a component is of utmost importance.	Extremely likely	Middleware is the "hearth" of the whole system, without its existence the communication between components is not feasible.	No
Data Integration Module	SIMAVI	METICOS will integrate with various data sources with different formats. The problem is the distributed nature of this data and the diversity of data formats. The data should be centralized and the format standardized in order to minimize work at component level in order to access and convert the data.	The causes are the heterogenous nature of the infrastructure at BCP level. The consequences are increased effort to access and used the data.	Very likely	It will offer a centralized access to the data	No

Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module	ICCS	In our case, the problem the component tries to solve is the following: there is a multitude of structured data (we refer mostly to ratings/ Quality of Service metrics or raw data - such as time to cross the border, False Positive Rates, Waiting time...) available (open source or generated by the ICT infrastructure of the Border Control Points) that is not currently leveraged in order to derive conclusions about the social acceptance and quality of service of SBC technologies.	We can speculate that the cause of the problem is the lack of an organized attempt to measure societal acceptance as well as the lack of the necessary systems. The consequences is that currently there is no way of measuring the quality of service indicators that might influence the acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies in each BCP. At the moment, we have not identified any relevant work or European project in this direction, thus we think that the problem will persist without our intervention.	At the moment, we have not identified any relevant work or European project in this direction, thus we think that the problem will persist without our intervention.	The purpose of the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module is to process and analyze structured data from the aforementioned sources in order to uncover the correlations amongst variables of the raw data, regarding the technology acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies. Therefore, it is easy to deduce that it serves as a solution to the aforementioned problem.	Yes. From literature review, in other sectors, we have identified that the use of Big Data Analytics is the most appropriate approach to solve our problem, so we have not considered other alternatives. Other alternatives that we have considered are the typical Questionnaires which will be implemented in the context of other work packages.
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module	ICCS	In our case, the problem the component tries to solve is the following: there is a multitude of unstructured data (we refer mostly to textual data) available (open source or generated by the	We can speculate that the cause of the problem is the lack of an organized attempt to measure social acceptance as well as lack of the required system. Moreover, from the	From the literature review, we have not seen any relevant work that will solve the problem we have identified, thus we think that the problem will	The aim of the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module is to gather and analyze unstructured data from different	Yes. From literature review, in other sectors, we have identified that the use of Big Data Analytics is the most appropriate approach to solve our problem.

		<p>ICT infrastructure of the Border Control Points) that are not currently leveraged in order to derive conclusions about the user and social acceptance and quality of service of SBC technologies.</p>	<p>literature review, we notice that there are more and more efforts taking into account the User Generated Content of social media (Twitter, online reviews..) in order to understand customer/user/passenger quality of experience in relation to quality of service metrics. Still, most efforts concentrate in the use of surveys, which is not cost and time efficient.</p>	<p>persist without our intervention</p>	<p>sources, such as social media and Border Control Points (textual) data. Therefore, it is easy to deduce that it serves as a solution to the aforementioned problem.</p>	<p>Other alternatives that we have considered are the typical Questionnaires which will be implemented in the context of other work packages.</p>
<p>Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module</p>	<p>ICSS</p>	<p>In our case, the problem the component tries to solve is the following: at the moment, certain Border Control Points do not have all data required to accurately deduce the correlations between various factors and the acceptance of SBC technologies. Therefore, it becomes crucial to be able to build on existing data sources from various BCPs and extract knowledge from these data from various</p>	<p>We can speculate that the cause of the problem is the lack of the harmonization of the IT systems for BCPs.</p>	<p>At the moment, we have not identified any relevant work or European project in this direction, thus we think that the problem will persist without our intervention.</p>	<p>The purpose of the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Mechanisms module is to infer the acceptance of a BCP or technology by aggregating and analyzing data from different sources, locations and formats. Therefore, it is easy to deduce that it serves as a solution to the</p>	<p>From literature review, in other sectors, we have identified that the use of Big Data Analytics is the most appropriate approach to solve our problem, so we have not considered other alternatives.</p>

		sources, locations and formats.			aforementioned problem.	
Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA)	ICSS	In our case, the problem the component tries to solve is the following: currently, there is no way of visualizing neither the raw data nor the outputs of the Data Analytics applied to it.	We can speculate that the cause of the problem is the lack of the respective systems to visualize of raw BCP specific data in the form of interactive customizable dashboards and the lack of a Big Data Analytics platform to generate the results of the analysis. The consequences is that currently there is no way of visualizing the factors that influence the acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies (aggregated and individually).	At the moment, we have not identified any relevant work or European project in this direction, thus we think that the problem will persist without our intervention.	The aim of the Interactive Visual Analytics Technologies component is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyze correlations of data generated from ADME, Cross-Sectorial big data analytics as well as other METICOS components. Therefore, it is easy to deduce that it serves as a solution to the aforementioned problem.	We have considered the approach of an interactive web application/dashboard to be the most appropriate approach to solve our problem, and we have not considered other alternatives.
Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module	AIT	Prediction of likelihood of acceptance/utilization of a given border control (BC) technology by a specific person, understanding of the main drivers of acceptance/non-acceptance	Lack of uptake/societal acceptance, issues at BCP (e.g. congestion), bad technology choices, missed opportunities for securing positive impact	Accurate prediction might not be possible for all technologies, user segments, contexts (due to lack of ground truth data)	The component will materialize a proven, quantifiable approach towards understanding and predicting acceptance/non-acceptance	Yes: Qualitative interviews, usability and user experience questionnaires

			of BC technology deployment			
Social Toolkit Module composed of the socio-cultural framework and automated tools for assessing threshold	NTNU	For the socio-cultural framework, the problem is that the interaction between humans and technology is influenced by a number of social and psychological factors and characteristics. So, the individuals with different socio-cultural backgrounds have different acceptance rate/criteria for smart border control technologies.	The cause of the problem are different social and cultural backgrounds (level of education, cultural dimensions and values etc.) which influence the level of technologies acceptance. The consequences of the problem is rejection of use / acceptance.	The likelihood is very high	The social cultural models will assist system developers/ and border authorities to understand how users/individuals come to accept and use the technology. Also, the METICOS socio-cultural framework will give the opportunity to better engage/encourage the individuals to consider using the smart border control technologies.	No
		For the automated tools for assessing threshold, the problem is that each of the non-EU travelers have different level of interaction and expectation while using each of the BCP technology which affects the adjustment of the threshold considering all possibilities.	The causes of the problem are a) complexity of technology used, b) flexibility while using technology, c) available guidance from border staff and d) personal interest to use the BCP technology. The consequence is the difficulty in defining threshold values for non-	the likelihood is very high	Our component is being considered for solution to this problem because, this component is already taking in account all the groups (e.g. EU/non-EU travelers, border staffs), their interactions with the technology, response	No

			EU travelers for each of the BCP technology considering all possibilities		and waiting time while using technology and other relevant data attributes.	
Personnel Front-End	MAGG	The Front-End of METICOS is the Graphical User Interface of the whole system, including visual analytics to enable human-information discourse, a user-friendly design based on human cognitive and perceptual principles as well as efficient interaction methodologies software infrastructure that enables the interfaces to the corresponding back-end system	A poorly designed front-end will not help border control authorities and by the time will be out of use.	Extremely likely	Users (personnel) interact with the system through Front-End	No

4.1.3 Explanation and justification of lawfulness

Processing of personal data shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies⁵³:

- the data subject has given consent;
- processing is necessary for the performance of a contract;
- processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation;
- processing is necessary in order to protect vital interests;
- processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest;
- processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party.

The table 16 below identifies the lawfulness criteria applicable for the data being collected by each data source.

⁵³ See article 6 of the GDPR.

Table 16 - Explanation and justification of lawfulness

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Lawfulness criteria	Justification
Primary data	METICOS Mobile Application	Consent	<p>Article 4(11) of the GDPR defines consent as: “any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject’s wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her”.</p> <p>Appendix I contains an informed consent form that must be signed by every volunteer (traveller or border control staff member) willing to participate to the METICOS pilots during which primary data will be collected via the METICOS Mobile Application, the METICOS tablet application, TAM questionnaires and Twitter (using a dedicated - e.g. #METICOS-EU_pilot - hashtag).</p> <p>Consent is an appropriate lawful basis for travellers participating to METICOS pilots since they are offered control and a genuine choice with regard to accepting or declining the terms offered or declining them without detriment.</p> <p>As for border control staff participating to the METICOS pilots, consent would not be an appropriate lawful basis if the staff has no real choice, feels compelled to consent or would endure negative consequences if they do not consent. This could occur in the employment context in which, due to the dependency that results from the employer/employee relationship, border staff might be unable to deny his/her employer consent to data processing without experiencing the fear or real risk of detrimental effects as a result of a refusal. Therefore, in the context of the METICOS pilots, border staff are not giving their consent to their employer but to joint controllers (EUC, MAGG, NTNU, ICCS, JOAFG, NetU, SIMAVI and AIT) towards whom there is no imbalance of power.</p> <p>In case employees of the METICOS joint controllers are willing (or not) to participate to the METICOS pilots, it shall be ensured that their participation (or refusal) will have no adverse consequences. As an additional measure to guarantee free consent of joint controllers’</p>
Primary data	METICOS Tablet Application	Consent	
Primary data	Questionnaires	Consent	
Primary data	Twitter (After crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, the traveler is posting a tweet using a specific hashtag e.g. #METICOS-EU_pilot).	Consent	

			<p>employees, the consent form must be signed minimum two days before participating to the pilots. To some extent, this will ensure that employees are not pushed to participate.</p> <p>It should be underlined that primary data will only be collected from adult participants (over 18 years old).</p>
Secondary data	Twitter (and possibly other social media sources) collected for a long period of time which concern the public and societal acceptance of border control technologies.	Consent of the users to make tweets publicly available and legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers to further process these tweets for scientific and statistical purposes.	<p>The aim of processing tweets in the context of METICOS project is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Smart Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies. Through social media, users share self-expressions, opinions or general thoughts and publicly self-reported activities; these are posted more spontaneously through social media, no guidance needed, and the information provided could be used from context-aware systems. To retrieve this information, a Twitter data collector application downloads any related tweets periodically and provides them as input to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data module. Twitter is used as the source of information, due to the public character of users’ comments and the variety of information provided.</p> <p>When creating an account on Twitter, the data subjects agree with the terms and conditions of the Twitter’s privacy policy⁵⁴ according to which “By publicly posting content when you Tweet, you are directing us to disclose that information as broadly as possible, including through our APIs, and directing those accessing the information through our APIs to do the same. To facilitate the fast global dissemination of Tweets to people around the world, we use technology like application programming interfaces (APIs) and embeds to make that information available to websites, apps, and others for their use - for example, displaying Tweets on a news website or analyzing what people say on Twitter. We generally make this content available in limited quantities for free and charge licensing fees for large-scale access. We have standard terms that govern how this data can be used, and a compliance program to enforce these terms”.⁵⁵</p> <p>According to the Twitter standard terms that govern how public tweets can be used, “Unless explicitly approved otherwise by Twitter in writing, you may not use, or knowingly display,</p>

⁵⁴ The Twitter privacy policy is available at https://cdn.cms-twdigitalassets.com/content/dam/legal-twitter/site-assets/privacy-june-18th-2020/Twitter_Privacy_Policy_EN.pdf

⁵⁵ Ibid, p.5.

			<p>distribute, or otherwise make Twitter Content, or information derived from Twitter Content, available to any entity for the purpose of: (a) conducting or providing surveillance or gathering intelligence, including but not limited to investigating or tracking Twitter users or Twitter Content; (b) conducting or providing analysis or research for any unlawful or discriminatory purpose, or in a manner that would be inconsistent with Twitter users' reasonable expectations of privacy; (c) monitoring sensitive events (including but not limited to protests, rallies, or community organizing meetings); or (d) targeting, segmenting, or profiling individuals based on sensitive personal information, including their health (e.g., pregnancy), negative financial status or condition, political affiliation or beliefs, racial or ethnic origin, religious or philosophical affiliation or beliefs, sex life or sexual orientation, trade union membership, Twitter Content relating to any alleged or actual commission of a crime, or any other sensitive categories of personal information prohibited by law”⁵⁶.</p> <p>The basis of lawfulness for the collection of publicly available tweets is the consent of the data subject. The basis of lawfulness for the further compatible use of tweets for scientific research is the legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers. Indeed, the “compatibility presumption” provided by Article 5 (1) (b) of the GDPR states that “further processing for [...] scientific research purposes [...] shall, in accordance with Article 89 (1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes”. According to the Article 29 Working Party, “the fact that personal data is publicly available may be considered as a factor in the assessment, especially if the publication was carried out with a reasonable expectation of further use of the data for certain purposes (e.g. for purposes of research)⁵⁷”.</p>
Secondary data	Blogs/Websites	Consent of the users to make online reviews publicly available and legitimate interest of the METICOS joint	The basis of lawfulness for the further compatible use of online reviews for scientific research is the legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers. Indeed, the “compatibility presumption” provided by Article 5 (1) (b) of the GDPR states that “further processing for [...] scientific research purposes [...] shall, in accordance with Article 89 (1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes”. According to the Article 29 Working Party, “the fact that

⁵⁶ See the Twitter Developer Agreement at <https://developer.twitter.com/en/developer-terms/agreement>

⁵⁷ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 06/2014 on the notion of legitimate interests of the data controller under Article 7 of Directive 95/46/EC, adopted on 9 April 2014, WP217, p.39.

		controllers to further process these online reviews for scientific and statistical purposes.	personal data is publicly available may be considered as a factor in the assessment, especially if the publication was carried out with a reasonable expectation of further use of the data for certain purposes (e.g. for purposes of research)” ⁵⁸ .
Secondary data	Anonymized data collected from border crossing points	No basis of lawfulness needed.	The GDPR does not apply to anonymized data. The anonymization processes carried out by the end-user organizations (border crossing points) will be detailed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

⁵⁸ Ibidem.

In the table above, it is indicated that consent is the basis of lawfulness for the collection of primary data. It is important to note that this is legitimate as long as the data controllers of the METICOS platform are not border control authorities. Indeed, Recital 43 of the GDPR clearly indicates that it is unlikely that public authorities can rely on consent for processing as whenever the controller is a public authority, there is often a clear imbalance of power in the relationship between the controller and the data subject. Hence, after the end of the METICOS project, should the METICOS platform be used in real world conditions, it is strongly recommended no to allow any border control authority to act as data controller of the METICOS platform.

4.1.4 Explanation and justification of data minimization

Article 5, §1, c) of the GDPR imposes personal data to be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed”.

The principle of “data minimization” means that a data controller should limit the collection of personal information to what is directly relevant and necessary to accomplish a specified purpose. In other words, data controllers should collect only the personal data they really need to pursue their aim.

In the context of METICOS, the purpose of the platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions. Given this specified purpose, it was decided:

- Not to collect data from camera for behavior & emotion detection of travelers/border control staff. It was considered that the use of cameras for behavior & emotion detection could potentially lead to a “function creep”. This means that such data might have been used by border control authorities beyond the limits of the research purposes in order to support measures or decisions taken with regard to travelers (profiling/risk management/etc.).
- Not to collect data from travel documents. It was considered that it is not necessary for the purposes of the METICOS project to collect information enabling the individualization of each traveler/border control staff member (first name, last name, date of birth, etc.). Indeed, for the purposes of the project, it is only necessary to collect some generic demographic data (Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Frequent Flyer, Travel Habits/Experience, Level of Education, Sex, Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background/Orientation, Trust in BC Authorities, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence + Current occupation, Current work status [employed-unemployed-self-employed], per traveler or Rank, Work Experience, per staff member). Such demographic data is collected via the METICOS Mobile Application, the METICOS Tablet Application and Questionnaires. This alternative also offers more transparency during the data collection.

- Not to collect data from biometric sensors (e-gates, scanners, etc.) at border crossing points. It was considered that such data collection is not needed for the purposes of the project. Instead, it was decided that obtaining statistics about their use was sufficient (Number of access attempts with documents not accepted by the system; Number of access attempts with non-eligible documents; Number of complaints regarding SBC technologies (by date); Downtime of system per month/year; False Accept Rate / False Reject Rate; Total verification time; Total access time; Total time of biometric and document verification).
- Not to collect personal data from Border Control Databases such as VIS, SIS, etc. It was considered that such extremely sensitive data and was absolutely not needed for the purposes of the project.

Below you will find a table for listing the data processed, reduced to what is strictly necessary, alongside the justification of the need and any additional minimization controls.

Table 17 - Data minimization controls

Horizontal categorization	Data source	Data asset description	Details about the data processed	Justification of the need and relevance of the data	Minimization controls
Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> METICOS Mobile Application METICOS Tablet Application Questionnaires 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time to cross the border Travelers' demographics & profile Staff member demographics & profile Smiley face Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes Unstructured data in form of free text questions 	See tables 4, 5 and 6 for details.	The information collected via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet applications as well as via questionnaires is absolutely necessary to achieve the purposes of the project.	<p>No “direct identifiers” (first name, last name, date of birth, etc.) is being collected.</p> <p>Data will also be anonymized. The anonymization processes will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.</p>
Primary data	Twitter	Tweet after completing use case METICOS pilot.	After crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, the traveler is posting a tweet using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag.	The information collected via Twitter is very relevant in order to measure the acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies.	See next line.
Secondary data	Twitter		Tweets (or other) collected for a long period of time which concern the public	The information collected via Twitter is very relevant in order to measure the acceptance	<p>Tweets will be anonymized.</p> <p>The only information kept is the aggregated results from the analysis</p>

		Tweets (or other) regarding acceptance of Border Control Technologies.	and societal acceptance of border control technologies.	and efficiency of border control technologies.	performed above (sentiment, context of discussion, topics identified, geographic distribution, ...). The anonymization process will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.
Secondary data	Blogs/Websites	Online reviews of BCPs	Online reviews which concern specific BCPs (airports/ports/land borders).	Information contained in online reviews published on Blogs and Websites are very relevant to measure the acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies.	Personal data contained in online reviews will be removed (anonymization). What is needed for the METICOS platform is only the sentiment analysis deriving from the online review. How this process is carried out is currently being examined and will be reported in in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26
Secondary data	Anonymized data from border crossing points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Checked passengers per flight/day • Waiting Time - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/per hour) • Waiting Time - manual control (average per passenger/per hour) 	See table 10 for details.	Anonymized statistics about waiting time, queue length, number of passengers being controlled, demographic profiles, travel routes, False Accept Rate / False Reject Rate etc. are absolutely necessary for the purposes of measuring the efficiency	Anonymization is being applied by the end-user organizations before transmitting the information to the METICOS platform. The anonymization processes carried out by the end-user organizations will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Queue length - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/ per hour) • Queue length - manual control (average per passenger/ per hour) • Number of passengers controlled by Border Guard (per month/per hour) • Number of passengers who used ABC technologies (per month/per hour) • Passenger Demographics & Profiles • Recurring travelers per origin/destination • Historical passenger data • Number of access attempts with documents not accepted by the system - For BCP technologies 		<p>of border control technologies</p>	
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of complaints regarding SBC technologies (by date) • Downtime of system per month/year - For BCP technologies • FAR / FRR - For BCP technologies • Total verification time - For BCP technologies • Total access time - For BCP technologies • Total time of biometric and document verification - For BCP technologies • Flight delays 			
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4.1.5 Management of sensitive data

The GDPR foresees additional safeguards for certain types of personal data which are considered to be “sensitive”. Although the Regulation does not explicitly list the categories of sensitive data, such a list can be deduced from several provisions of the GDPR:

- Article 9 of the GDPR lists the “special categories of personal data” as follows: “data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation”;
- Furthermore, article 10 considers as being “sensitive” data “relating to criminal convictions and offences or related security measures”;
- In addition, the Article 29 Working Party considers that “beyond these provisions of the GDPR, some categories of data can be considered as increasing the possible risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals. These personal data are considered as sensitive (as this term is commonly understood) because they are linked to household and private activities (such as electronic communications whose confidentiality should be protected), or because they impact the exercise of a fundamental right (such as location data whose collection questions the freedom of movement) or because their violation clearly involves serious impacts in the data subject’s daily life (such as financial data that might be used for payment fraud)”⁵⁹.

In the context of METICOS, it should be highlighted that article 9, §2, j) of the GDPR allows the processing of sensitive data for scientific purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) if proportionate to the aim pursued, respects the essence of the right to data protection and provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.

As a general rule, when establishing the list of primary and secondary data needed to feed the METICOS platform, the consortium paid attention to minimize as much as possible the collection of “sensitive” data in the sense of the aforementioned provisions of the GDPR. However, table 17 below lists certain types of categories of data which deserve specific attention and details appropriate mitigation measures being adopted.

It should also be emphasized that anonymous data originating from border crossing points’ databases and being further processed by the METICOS platform are considered to be non-sensitive for privacy⁶⁰. As already mentioned, further details about the anonymization processes carried out by the end-user organizations will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26”. However, the processing of anonymous data may have other human rights or societal implications. Indeed, according to the Council of Europe, “since Big Data makes it possible to collect and analyze large amounts of data to identify attitude patterns and predict behaviors of groups and communities, the collective dimension of the risks related to the use of data [should] also be

⁵⁹ Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP 248 rev.01, as last Revised and Adopted on 4 October 2017, pp. 9-10.

⁶⁰ As a reminder, the GDPR does not apply the processing of anonymous data. See Recital 26 of the GDPR.

considered”⁶¹. These human rights’ implications of the METICOS platform are being examined in D3.2 – “Human rights impact assessment (first version)” and in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)”.

⁶¹ Council of Europe, Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of Big Data, Strasbourg, 23 January 2017, p.3.

Table 18 - Management of sensitive data

Horizontal categorization	Data source(s)	Data asset description	Data deserving specific attention	Mitigation measures
Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • METICOS mobile application • METICOS tablet application • Questionnaires 	Travelers' demographics & profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contains “Cultural Background/Orientation”. • Contains “Need for special attention/assistance” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data concerning cultural background is needed for the purpose of the project purpose. Such data might reveal racial or ethnic origin as well as religious or philosophical beliefs. In order to avoid negative consequences for the data subjects (participants), all answers to the questions in the METICOS mobile & tablet applications as well as in questionnaires are anonymized. • Data concerning the need for special attention/assistance is important for the project purpose. The questions will be drafted so as to avoid collection of sensitive data in the meaning of the GDPR. The data will also be anonymized. • Data about impacts on personal health/wellbeing is important for the project purpose. The possible answers to the questions will be structured so as to avoid
		Staff member demographics & profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contains “Cultural Background/Orientation”. • Contains “Need for special attention/assistance” 	
		Structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes	Contains “any impact on personal health/wellbeing”	

				collection of too detailed data concerning health. In any case, information about specific diseases/health problems will not be collected. The data will also be anonymized.
		Unstructured data in form of free text questions	Contains “What problems have you encountered while using SBC technologies?”	The data subject will be informed that he/she should avoid transmitting detailed data about his/her health or other sensitive data when entering free text. The data will also be anonymized.
Primary data	Twitter	After crossing the border in the METICOS pilot site, the user is posting a tweet using a dedicated – e.g. #METICOS-EU_pilot- hashtag.	The tweet posted using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag might contain sensitive data	The data subject will be informed that he/she should avoid transmitting sensitive data on Twitter using the dedicated METICOS pilot hashtag. Tweets will be anonymized.
Secondary data	Twitter	Tweets (or other) collected for a long period of time which concern the public and societal acceptance of border control technologies.	The tweet’s texts collected by the Twitter data collector might contain sensitive information.	Tweets will be anonymized.
Secondary data	Blogs/Websites	Online reviews which concern specific BCPs (airports/ports/land borders).	Online reviews might contain sensitive information.	Personal data contained in online reviews will be removed (anonymization). What is needed for the METICOS platform is only the sentiment analysis deriving from the online review.

Secondary data	Data from border crossing points	Anonymized statistics	Anonymized statistics originating from border crossing points are not considered sensitive from a privacy point of view.	N/A
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4.1.6 Anonymization processes applied to primary and secondary data

In order to meet the specificities of processing personal data for scientific research purposes in the context of METICOS, specific attention should be drawn to article 89 of the GDPR according to which “processing for [...] scientific research purposes shall be subject to appropriate safeguards [...] for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organizational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimization. Those measures may include pseudonymization provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner”.

In other words, article 89 of the GDPR recommends “anonymization” of data processed for research purposes. If this is not feasible, the possibility of “pseudonymization” of data should be examined. The concepts of “anonymization” and “pseudonymization” are examined hereunder:

- “Anonymization” of data means processing it with the aim of irreversibly preventing the identification of the individual to whom it relates. Data can be considered anonymized when it does not allow identification of the individuals to whom it relates, and it is not possible that any individual could be identified from the data by any further processing of that data or by processing it together with other information, which is available or likely to be available.
- “Pseudonymization” of data consists of replacing one attribute (typically a unique attribute) in a record by another. The natural person is therefore still likely to be identified indirectly⁶². Pseudonymization should be distinguished from anonymization, as it only provides a limited protection for the identity of data subjects because it still allows identification using indirect means. Indeed, where a pseudonym is used, it is possible to identify the data subject by analyzing the underlying or related data. In other words, pseudonymization is not a method of anonymization. It merely reduces the linkability of a dataset with the original identity of a data subject, and is accordingly a useful security measure. The most known pseudonymization techniques are counter, random number generator, encryption with secret key and hash function⁶³.

In the context of the METICOS platform, it is considered that the purpose of the project could be achieved :

1. by anonymizing the primary data collected via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications and questionnaires before presenting the KPIs and metrics to border control authorities and decision makers;

⁶² The GDPR defines pseudonymization as follows: “the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person”.

⁶³ For an overview of pseudonymization techniques, see ENISA, Pseudonymisation techniques and best practices, Recommendations on shaping technology according to data protection and privacy provisions, 2019.

2. by anonymizing the primary and secondary data collected via Twitter before presenting the KPIs and metrics to border control authorities and decision makers;
3. by collecting already anonymized statistical secondary data originating from end-user organizations (Border Control Points).

In order to anonymize personal data, the data must be stripped of sufficient elements such that the data subject can no longer be identified. More precisely, the data must be processed in such a way that it can no longer be used to identify a natural person by using “all the means likely reasonably to be used” by either the controller or a third party. An important factor is that the processing must be irreversible. The GDPR does not clarify how such a deidentification process should or could be performed. The focus is on the outcome: that data should be such as not to allow the data subject to be identified via “all” “likely” and “reasonable” means.

According to the Article 29 Working party, “an effective anonymisation solution prevents all parties from singling out an individual in a dataset, from linking two records within a dataset (or between two separate datasets) and from inferring any information in such dataset. Generally speaking, therefore, removing directly identifying elements in itself is not enough to ensure that identification of the data subject is no longer possible. It will often be necessary to take additional measures to prevent identification, once again depending on the context and purposes of the processing for which the anonymised data are intended”⁶⁴. Different anonymisation practices and techniques exist with variable degrees of robustness. According to ENISA, “most anonymization techniques can be classified in two main families. A first family includes k-anonymity and its extensions taking care of attribute disclosure, like p-sensitive k-anonymity, l-diversity, t-closeness, (n,t)-closeness, and others. The second family is built around the notion of ϵ -differential privacy”.

An effective anonymization process must be protected against three major risks:

- Singling out, which corresponds to the possibility to isolate some or all records which identify an individual in the dataset;
- Linkability, which is the ability to link, at least, two records concerning the same data subject or a group of data subjects (either in the same database or in two different databases). If an attacker can establish (e.g. by means of correlation analysis) that two records are assigned to a same group of individuals but cannot single out individuals in this group, the technique provides resistance against “singling out” but not against linkability;
- Inference, which is the possibility to deduce, with significant probability, the value of an attribute from the values of a set of other attributes.

The table below describes how the choice for the anonymization techniques applied to the different data categories will be made.

Table 19 - Anonymization techniques

Data categories	Anonymization process
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⁶⁴ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques, adopted on 10 April 2014, WP216, p.9.

<p>Primary data collected via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications and questionnaires</p>	<p>When collecting primary data via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications and questionnaires, the joint controllers will not ask for any directly identifiers such as first name, last name, date of birth, etc.</p> <p>In addition, the responsible partners for developing the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications (MAGG) and questionnaires (AIT) will select appropriate anonymization techniques. The choice and description of this anonymization process will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.</p>
<p>Primary and secondary data collected via Twitter</p>	<p>The Twitter data collector application downloads any related tweets periodically and provides them as input to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data module. The data retrieved are the date and time the tweet has been posted, the tweet’s text, the tweet ID, number of retweets and likes, and the tweet’s location. All other information is discarded. The ADME for Unstructured Data module uses the information provided by the Twitter data collector application as input, aiming to process the tweet’s text and derive the overall sentiment of the tweets, their geographic distribution, topics identified, and the context of discussion (most popular hashtags and mentions, topics people are tweeting about, entities identified in text, such as people, locations, organizations etc.). After having retrieved the above information, the tweets are deleted. The only information being kept is the aggregated results from the analysis performed above (sentiment, context of discussion, geographic distribution).</p> <p>At this stage of the project, the anonymization techniques currently being envisaged by ICCS are generalization, data masking and data substitution. The choice and description of the anonymization process will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.</p>
<p>Statistical secondary data collected from Border crossing points (end-user organizations)</p>	<p>At this stage of the project, the consortium is verifying with the end-user organizations (MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS, CYPOL) whether the statistical data listed in table 10 is available and can be shared with the METICOS joint controllers.</p> <p>Once the availability of the end-users’ data will be confirmed and in order to ensure that the anonymization processes will be carried out effectively by the end-user organizations before that the information is transmitted to the METICOS platform, it is planned to organize a workshop with MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS and CYPOL. This workshop will be dedicated to discuss the anonymization techniques being applied in order to avoid risks of re-identification. These</p>

	anonymization techniques will be detailed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.
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4.1.7 Explanation and justification of data quality

Below you will find a table for setting out in detail the data quality compliance controls as well as a justification on the arrangements for or impossibility of implementing them.

Table 20 - Data quality controls

Data categories	Data quality controls
Primary data are collected via the METICOS Mobile & Tablet Applications and questionnaires	These data are being directly collected from volunteer participants which have been informed about the METICOS project aim and objectives. It is being considered that data directly provided by participants are relevant, accurate and up to date.
Primary and secondary data collected via Twitter	Data publicly published on Twitter is considered to reflect the accurate opinions of their authors.
Statistical secondary data collected from Border crossing points (end-user organizations)	Statistical data provided by the end-user organizations is considered to be trustable. The temporal coverage of the statistics being provided by the end-user organizations will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

4.1.8 Explanation and justification of storage durations

A storage duration must be defined for each type of data and justified by the legal requirements and/or processing needs. Functional traces will also have to be purged, as will technical logs which may not be stored indefinitely.

Table 21 - Storage durations

Data source or component	Storage duration	Justification of the storage duration	Erasure mechanism at the end of the storage duration
Questionnaires	To be defined	To be defined	To be defined
METICOS Mobile Application	To be defined	To be defined	To be defined

METICOS Tablet Application	To be defined	To be defined	To be defined
METICOS servers (Data Integration Module)	To be defined	To be defined	To be defined
End-user Front-End	To be defined	To be defined	To be defined

At this stage of the project, the storage duration of the data processed by the METICOS platform has not been defined yet. At the latest, it is envisaged to delete the collected personal data at the end of the project’ lifetime but this needs to be confirmed. In any case, further detailed information about the technological aspects of the IT systems on which the data rely and the storage duration will be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

4.1.9 Assessment of the controls

Table 22 - Assessment of fundamental principles

Controls guaranteeing the proportionality and necessity of the processing	Acceptable/can be improved on?	Corrective controls
Purposes: specified, explicit and legitimate	Acceptable	If necessary, this will be updated and reviewed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” due on M26.
Basis: lawfulness of processing, prohibition of misuse	Acceptable	If necessary, this will be updated and reviewed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” due on M26.
Data minimization: adequate, relevant and limited	Can be improved	The anonymization techniques need to be precisely defined in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” due on M26. This is

		important in order to mitigate risks of re-identification.
Data quality: accurate and kept up-to-date	Can be improved	Additional details about the exact data provided by the end-user organizations will be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” due on M26.
Storage durations: limited	This still must be defined.	This will be defined in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” due on M26.

4.2 Controls protecting data subjects’ rights

The aim of this sub-section is to:

- Identify or determine, and describe, the controls (existing or planned) selected to comply with the following legal requirements (it is necessary to explain how it is intended to implement them):
 1. information for the data subjects;
 2. obtaining consent, where applicable;
 3. exercising the data subject’s rights and the applicable exemptions;
 4. processors: identified and governed by a contract;
 5. transfers: compliance with the obligations bearing on transfer of data outside the European Union.

4.2.1 Information for the data subjects

Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR lists the information that must be provided to the data subjects in order to be fair and transparent:

- the identity of the joint controllers ;
- the contact details of the representative of the joint controllers;
- the contact details of the data protection officer, where applicable;
- the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis for the processing;
- the categories of personal data concerned;
- the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data, if any;
- where applicable, that the controller intends to transfer personal data to a recipient in a third country or international organization as well as the applicable safeguards;

- the period for which the personal data will be stored, or if that is not possible, the criteria used to determine that period;
- where the processing is based on point (f) of Article 6(1), the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party;
- where processing is based on point (a) of Article 6(1) or point (a) of Article 9(2), the existence of the right to withdraw consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- the existence and exemptions to the rights of the data subjects;
- the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority;
- from which source the personal data originate, and if applicable, whether it came from publicly accessible sources;
- whether the provision of personal data is a statutory or contractual requirement, or a requirement necessary to enter into a contract, as well as whether the data subject is obliged to provide the personal data and of the possible consequences of failure to provide such data;
- where applicable, the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.

For secondary data, it should be noted that article 14, §5, b) foresees an exemption to inform data subjects when “the provision of such information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort, in particular for processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in Article 89(1) or in so far as the obligation referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the objectives of that processing. In such cases the controller shall take appropriate measures to protect the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, including making the information publicly available”.

For each data source, the table below details how the right to information is being implemented in the METICOS platform.

Table 23 - Controls for the right to information

Horizontal categorization	Data sources	Implementation
Primary data	Questionnaires	The information sheet (see Appendix) is provided to the participants providing data via questionnaires, the applications and twitter.
Primary data	METICOS Mobile Application	
Primary data	METICOS Tablet Application	
Primary data	After crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, the traveler is posting a tweet	

	in the using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag.	
Secondary data	Tweets (or other) collected for a long period of time which concern the public and societal acceptance of border control technologies	The provision of information would involve a disproportionate effort, in particular for processing scientific research purposes. Appropriate measures are considered to be implemented since that the data is being anonymized before being accessible via the End-user Front-End to border control authorities and decision makers.
Secondary data	Online reviews from Blogs & Websites	On the METICOS project’s website, the joint controllers will make publicly available the information according to which public tweets and online reviews are being further processed for research purposes.
Secondary data	Anonymized and statistical data originating from border crossing points’ databases	This requirement is not applicable to already anonymized data.

4.2.2 Determination and description of the controls for obtaining explicit consent

For each data source, when applicable, the table below details how the METICOS platform complies with the requirement of obtaining informed consent of participants.

Table 24 - Controls for obtaining consent

Horizontal categorization	Data sources	Implementation
Primary data	Questionnaires	The informed consent form (see Appendix) must be signed by the participants before providing data via questionnaires, the applications and twitter.
Primary data	METICOS Mobile Application	
Primary data	METICOS Tablet Application	
Primary data	After crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, the traveler is posting a tweet in the using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag.	

Secondary data	Tweets (or other) collected for a long period of time which concern the public and societal acceptance of border control technologies	The basis of lawfulness for the collection of these secondary data is not consent. The basis of lawfulness for the further compatible use of tweets and online reviews for scientific research is the legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers. Indeed, the “compatibility presumption” provided by Article 5 (1) (b) of the GDPR states that “further processing for [...] scientific research purposes [...] shall, in accordance with Article 89 (1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes”. According to the Article 29 Working Party, “the fact that personal data is publicly available may be considered as a factor in the assessment, especially if the publication was carried out with a reasonable expectation of further use of the data for certain purposes (e.g. for purposes of research)” ⁶⁵ .
Secondary data	Online reviews from Blogs & Websites	
Secondary data	Anonymized and statistical data originating from border crossing points’ databases	This requirement is not applicable to already anonymized data.

4.2.3 Exemption to the rights of the data subjects

In principle, article 7, §3 of the GDPR requires that the data subject shall have the right to withdraw his or her consent at any time. Moreover, articles 15 to 20 of the GDPR foresee different rights for the data subjects amongst which the rights of access, rectification and erasure.

However, article 11 of the GDPR foresees an exemption as follows: “if the purposes for which a controller processes personal data do not or do no longer require the identification of a data subject by the controller, the controller shall not be obliged to maintain, acquire or process additional information in order to identify the data subject for the sole purpose of complying with this Regulation”.

When collecting primary data and secondary data, the METICOS joint controllers do not acquire any direct identifier such as first name, last name, date of birth, email-address, etc. The reason of such

⁶⁵ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 06/2014 on the notion of legitimate interests of the data controller under Article 7 of Directive 95/46/EC, adopted on 9 April 2014, WP217, p.39.

data minimization is that the identification of a data subject by the joint controllers is not needed for the purposes of the METICOS platform.

By consequence, in accordance with article 11, §2 of the GDPR, “where, in cases referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article, the controller is able to demonstrate that it is not in a position to identify the data subject, the controller shall inform the data subject accordingly, if possible”. In such cases, the rights of the data subjects shall not apply except where the data subject, for the purpose of exercising his or her rights, provides additional information enabling his or her identification. In order to comply with the conditions of this exemption, the informed consent (see Appendix) contains a special clause informing the data subjects that the METICOS joint controllers are not in a position to identify the data subjects and that for that reason, the rights of the data subjects cannot be exercised, except if a data subject provides additional information enabling his or her identification.

4.2.4 Controls applicable to processors

This section of CNIL’s methodology does not apply since that no data processors are identified at this stage of the project. At this stage of the project, it is envisaged to store the data processed by the METICOS platform on METICOS’s servers. Potentially, at a later stage of the project, the use of an external Cloud solution may be examined. In this event, the identification of the data processor (the Cloud provider) and the GDPR compliance of this solution will be carried out in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

4.2.5 Controls on transfer of data outside the European Union

At this stage of the project, no data transfers outside the European Union are being envisaged.

METICOS will be demonstrated and validated both at land border and airports. This will involve two use case scenarios in four pilot areas (Greece, Cyprus, Romania, Estonia). Due to data protection and data privacy matters, it is still under consideration to have a fifth pilot (Ukraine), which is a third country (outside of the EU and the EEA). If this fifth pilot in Ukraine is confirmed, the privacy implications and mitigation measures will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” which is due on M26.

5 Management of the privacy risks

5.1 Assessment of existing or planned controls

This section should identify or determine the existing or planned controls (already undertaken), which can take three different forms:

1. controls bearing specifically on the data being processed: encryption, anonymization, partitioning, access control, traceability, etc.;
2. general security controls regarding the system in which the processing is carried out: operating security, backups, hardware security, etc.;

In addition, in this section, it should be checked whether improving each control, pursuant to best security practices, is either not necessary or not possible.

5.1.1 Controls bearing specifically on the data being processed

At this stage of the project, the technical system architecture and specifications of the METICOS platform have not been defined yet. By consequence, in this first version of the DPIA, it is not feasible yet to describe in detail the envisaged security controls bearing specifically on the data being processed. Nonetheless, at this stage, it is already possible to provide a general description of the envisaged security objectives of the METICOS platform. The figure below describes a first draft of data flow diagram enriched with security features⁶⁶. As illustrated below:

- Statistical data originating from the border crossing points databases are anonymized before being sent to the METICOS platform.
- Logical access control verifies that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to the anonymized data originating from the border crossing points.
- Logical access control verifies that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to any primary or secondary data collected by the METICOS platform.
- Primary and secondary data are being encrypted when stored on the METICOS servers (in the Data integration module).
- After having been processed by the METICOS components, all primary and secondary data are being anonymized before being sent to the Personnel Front-End. The general security goal is to avoid that non-anonymized data could be made available to authorized border control authorities or decision makers. Indeed, the overall purpose of the METICOS platform is to provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers via the End-User Front-End. Hence access to non-anonymized data to the end-users should strictly be avoided.
- Access control verifies that only authorized border control authorities and decision makers have access to the anonymized data made available via the Personnel Front-End.

⁶⁶ This diagram could be modified during the duration of the project. A final diagram will be included in D3.6 - "Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)", due on M26.

Figure 6 - Data flow diagram enriched with security features

The table 25 below should describe and assess in detail the existing or planned controls bearing specifically on the data being processed. The information contained in this table will be completed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

Table 25 - Controls bearing specifically on the data being processed

Controls bearing specifically on the data being processed	Implementation or justification why not	Acceptable/can be improved on?	Corrective controls
Encryption	Envisaged to be implemented for all primary and secondary data stored on the METICOS servers.	Can be improved	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6
Anonymization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical data originating from the BCP databases are anonymized before being sent to the METICOS platform • All primary and secondary data are being anonymized after having been processed by the METICOS components and before being presented to the authorized border control authorities and decision makers. 	Can be improved	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6
Data partitioning (in relation to the rest of the information system)	It is recommended that METICOS servers consist into a dedicated IT environment .	Can be improved	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6
Logical access control and logging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logical access control is envisaged to be implemented to verify that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to the 	Can be improved	

	<p>statistical data originating from the border crossing points' databases.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logical access control is envisaged to be implemented to verify that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to any primary or secondary data collected by the METICOS platform. • Logical access control is envisaged to be implemented to verify that only authorized border control authorities and decision makers have access to the anonymized data made available via the Personnel Front-End. 		<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>
<p>Other ?</p>		<p>Can be improved</p>	<p>Possibly, other security measures will be added and detailed in D3.6.</p>

5.1.2 General security controls regarding the system in which the processing is carried out

At this stage of the project, the technical system architecture and specifications of the METICOS platform have not been defined yet. By consequence, in this first version of the DPIA, it is not feasible yet to describe in detail the envisaged general security controls regarding the system in which the processing is carried out. The table below will be completed in in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26. All the considered security control are based on ISO/IEC 27001:2013 standard⁶⁷. ISO/IEC 27001:2013 specifies the requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an information security management system within the context of the organization.

⁶⁷ ISO/IEC 27001:2013 Information technology — Security techniques — Information security management systems — Requirements.

Table 26 - General security controls regarding the system in which the processing is carried out

General security controls regarding the system in which the processing is carried out	Implementation or justification why not	Acceptable/can be improved on?	Corrective controls	Reference to ISO/IEC 27001:2013
METICOS policy and procedures	It is recommended to document the security policy and procedures.	Should be defined	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.5 Security policy
Operating security	It is recommended to describe how the software updates (operating systems, applications, etc.) and application of security corrective controls are carried out.	Must still be defined	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6	
Clamping down on malicious software	It is recommended to state here whether an antivirus software is installed and updated at regular intervals.	Must still be defined	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6	
Backups	It is recommended to indicate here how backups are managed and to clarify whether they are stored in a safe place.	Must still be defined	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.12.3 Back-Up

<p>Maintenance</p>	<p>It is recommended to describe here how physical maintenance of hardware is managed, and state whether this is contracted out.</p> <p>Indicate whether the remote maintenance of apps is authorized, and according to what arrangements.</p> <p>Specify whether defective equipment is managed in a specific manner.</p>	<p>Must still be defined</p>	<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>	
<p>Security of computer channels (networks)</p>	<p>It is recommended to indicate here the type of network on which the processing is carried out (isolated, private or Internet).</p> <p>Specify which firewall system, intrusion detection systems or other active or passive devices are in charge of ensuring network security.</p>	<p>Must still be defined</p>	<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.13 Communications Security
<p>Activity/event logging and monitoring</p>	<p>It is recommended to indicate here whether real-time monitoring of local network is</p>	<p>Must still be defined</p>	<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.12.4 Logging and monitoring

	<p>implemented and with what means.</p> <p>Indicate whether monitoring of hardware and software configurations is carried out and by what means.</p> <p>Ensure logging auditing and access to data should be based on need-to-know and least privileges principles.</p>			
<p>Physical access control and user access/privilege management</p>	<p>It is recommended to indicate here how physical access control is carried out regarding the premises accommodating the processing.</p> <p>Indicate whether there are warning procedures in place in the event of a break-in.</p> <p>The allocation of user access to data and user privileges should be implemented with an appropriate access control model such as Role-based access control.</p>	<p>Must still be defined</p>	<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.9.1 Business requirement of Access control policy • A.9.2 User access management • A.9.2.1 User registration and de- registration • A.11 Physical and environmental security

<p>Hardware security</p>	<p>It is recommended to indicate here the controls bearing on the physical security of servers and devices (secure storage, security cables, confidentiality filters, secure erasure prior to scrapping, etc.)</p>	<p>Must still be defined</p>	<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A. 14.1 Security requirements of information systems • A.11 Physical and environmental security • A. 6.2 Mobile devices and teleworking
<p>Protecting against non-human sources of risks</p>	<p>It is recommended to describe here the means of fire prevention, detection and fighting.</p> <p>Where applicable, indicate the means of preventing water damage.</p> <p>Also specify the means of power supply monitoring and relief.</p>	<p>Must still be defined</p>	<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.7 Human resource security • A.7.2.2 Information security awareness, education and training
<p>Data deletion/disposal</p>	<p>It is recommended to plan the data for the data deletion and provide all disposal policy and procedures.</p> <p>The disposal of data should include shredding of paper and portable media used to store personal data</p>	<p>Must be defined</p>	<p>This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A. 8.3.2 Disposal of media • A. 11.2.7 Secure disposal or re-use of equipment

	during the METCIOS pilot.			
Policy for METCIOS polit procedures and responsibilities	It is recommended to defined a clear policy and procedures for METCIOS pilot including (not limited to), timelines for the pilot, the roles/users, test needed, type of data should be processed etc.	Must be define	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.12.1.1 Documented operating procedures and responsibilities
Roles and responsibilities	It is recommended to define and allocate in accordance with METICOS polit' policy the role and responsibilities of each partners related to data protection	Must be define	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A.6.1.1 Information security roles and responsibilities • A6.1.2 Segregation of duty
Other	Possibly, other security measures will be added and detailed in D3.6.	Must still be defined	This measure needs to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6	

5.2 Risk assessment

On the grounds of the GDPR, risk is understood as a negative consequence arising from processing operations that might or might not occur in the future. Such a consequence, if it materialised, would produce physical, material or non-material damage to natural persons (largely, data subjects) and not solely to the controllers or processors. Risk assessment is meant to be as objective as possible (Recitals 75–76).

A typical method for risk assessment requires, first, the identification of a risk, i.e., to find, recognise and describe it. In the second step, the risk is analysed, i.e., its nature is comprehended in order to determine the level of risk. In the third step, the risk is evaluated, i.e., the results of risk analysis are

compared with the risk criteria in order to determine whether the risk and its level are acceptable, if any mitigation measure is to be recommended and if any risk should be prioritised.

The table below contains a basic risk assessment based on the envisaged controls described in this deliverable.

Table 27 - Risk assessment

Risks	Acceptable/can be improved on?	Corrective controls
Illegitimate access to data	Can be improved but if all controls envisaged in this Deliverable are confirmed, the risk is considered to be acceptable.	The controls being envisaged in this deliverable need to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6.
Unwanted change of data	Can be improved but if all controls envisaged in this Deliverable are confirmed, the risk is considered to be acceptable.	The controls being envisaged in this deliverable need to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6.
Disappearance of data	Can be improved but if all controls envisaged in this Deliverable are confirmed, the risk is considered to be acceptable.	The controls being envisaged in this deliverable need to be confirmed and detailed in D3.6.

5.3 Privacy risks

Risk	Acceptable/can be improved on?	Corrective controls
Deanonymization of the primary and secondary data being processed by the METICOS platform.	Can be improved	The choice and description of the anonymization mechanisms will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and

		recommendations (final version)” which is due on M26.
The data collected unfair or intrusive	Acceptable	DPIA is taken to evaluate and justify the necessity and proportionality
Data is unnecessarily collected without adequate justification	Acceptable	DPIA is taken to evaluate and justify the necessity and proportionality
Data subjects are not given enough information or warning about the purposes of the collection of data from them	Acceptable	METICOS information sheet provides all information needed.
Data is collected/used for purposes that are not what they were collected for.	Acceptable	DPIA is taken to ensure purpose limitation.
Data is retained longer than necessary	Can be improved	The storage duration of the data will be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.
Information sharing arrangement with other processors puts personal data at risk.	Can be improved	No processors have been identified at this stage of the project. This needs to be confirmed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.
Outsourcing to external suppliers does not adequately protect data.	Can be improved	No outsourcing of data in METICOS project.
Transfers of personal data to third countries (outside of the EU and EEA)	Can be improved	At this stage of the project, no data transfers outside the European Union are being envisaged. If the pilot in Ukraine is confirmed, the privacy implications and mitigation measures will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)” which is due on M26.
Authorization to access data is not controlled and there is unauthorized access to the data	Can be improved	Role and allocation of responsibilities of access should be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

<p>Data is incorrectly linked with a person which could lead to that person having an incorrect decision made against them.</p>	<p>Acceptable</p>	<p>No direct identifiers (name, date of birth) are collected during the collection of primary and secondary data.</p> <p>The consent form contains such direct identifiers (for accountability towards the European Commission) but the risk of linkability with the primary and secondary data being collected is considered as being low.</p>
<p>Collection and processing of personal data might discriminate individuals and or/violate human rights.</p>		<p>A Human Rights Impact Assessment is being conducted in D3.2 - “Human rights impact assessment (first version)” (M12) and in D3.7 – “Human rights impact assessment (final version)” (M30).</p>

6 Conclusions

The first version of the Data Protection Impact Assessment conducted in this Deliverable is based on the information made available by the METICOS joint controllers at this stage of the project. Therefore, it should be considered as an interim version. It concludes that if all controls described and envisaged in this Deliverable are being confirmed, detailed and implemented, the privacy risks are considered to be acceptable. However, given that the technical system architecture and specifications of the METICOS platform still need to be detailed, many aspects still need to be confirmed and it is possible that changes might arise. Being an iterative process, a final version of this DPIA will be provided in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M26.

In this first version of the DPIA, it was not feasible yet to seek the views of data subjects or their representatives. This step will be completed in D3.6 in accordance with the Description of Action (DoA) which requires that the impact assessment will “consult with relevant project stakeholders and external stakeholders (e.g., technical experts, lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, citizens, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, as well as others) to validate the analysis and suggest additional issues for consideration”.

The DoA also requires to “hold a virtual workshop to validate findings”. This will be carried out by gathering the opinion of the Ethical Advisory Board on the DPIA process. In addition, D3.6 will seek the advices of each partner’s DPOs. As a reminder the DPO of each partner’s organization has been identified in D1.3 (“POPD-Requirement No.5”).

APPENDIX: METICOS’ information sheet and informed consent forms

METICOS Information Sheet

METICOS Information Sheet

Project Title:

METICOS: A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

You are invited to participate in a research study being conducted as part of the research project METICOS. The project is coordinated by the European University of Cyprus (EUC) and is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 scheme (Grand Agreement number 883075). The project began on 01/09/2020 and will come to an end on 31/08/2023. You can find more about the project at website <https://meticos-project.eu/>.

Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to provide you a relevant information about objectives of METICOS project, the nature of your participation to METICOS activities, the personal data that will be collected and used by the METICOS platform and how the data will be protected to ensure data confidentiality and privacy as well as what are your rights with respect to your participation.

The METICOS: Concepts and objectives

The purpose of the METICOS platform is to conduct scientific research exploring both travellers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.

The METICOS joint controllers

The joint controllers of the METICOS platform are EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY CYPRUS (EUC), INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS (ICCS), NET-U CONSULTANTS LTD (NetU), NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU (NTNU), SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL (SIMAVI), AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH (AIT), JOHANNITER OSTERREICH AUSBILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH (JOAFG) and MAGGIOLI SPA (MAGG).

The METICOS joint controllers agreed that EUC may be contacted by the data subjects and represent the other joint controllers. The person to be contacted is the coordinator of the project, Pantelis Velanas. (may be contacted at P.Velanas@research.euc.ac.cy).

Basis of lawfulness

The basis of lawfulness for the collection of primary data is your consent. The basis of lawfulness for the collection of secondary data (twitter data) is the legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers to further process public data for scientific and statistical purposes.

Incidental findings

During the processing of your data, incidental findings may be found. In the event such incidental findings arise, this will be reported to the responsible persons and the European Commission. Findings will be evaluated and their deletion and communication to you will be considered. In case of incidental findings that include recording an illegal activity, METICOS will comply with all relevant local and international laws.

Recipients

Only authorized researchers of METICOS joint controllers' organizations will have access to the primary and secondary data being collected. Border control authorities and other decision makers will be provided only with anonymized metrics and KPIs.

Transborder data flows

No data transfers outside the European Union are being envisaged.

Data retention period

At the latest, personal data concerning you will be deleted four months after the end of the project.

Purposes of your participation

The purpose of your participation is to contribute to the validation of the technology acceptance, the social acceptance and to enhance the trust to Smart Border solutions by civilians from different cultures. The information collected during the study will be gathered together and used to contribute towards the project, its reports and a number of journal and conference publications. None of the information will identify you individually but will be analysed at an aggregate level.

[The information sheet shall be amended to provide for the required wording for each activity for the participant to understand the nature of participation in the research and the types of personal data that are collected:

WORKSHOPS AND INTERVIEWS;

You will be asked to participate in METICOS pilot that will take place at [place] on [time]. During the pilots you will be asked to use the available equipment in your capacity as a [border control officer OR traveller].

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire on the technologies and their applicability and usability in relation to the Border Control Points.

The data collected by METICOS:

The data to be collected will not contain any personal or sensitive information that can identify you. Any personal information (eg. Name, contact details etc) that may be collected from you is for our internal processing and administrative purposes only, and to enable to contact you if we require further information.

AND/OR

QUESTIONNAIRES AND SURVEYS;**Nature of participation:**

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire that will post questions in relation to border control points technologies, their efficiencies and societal acceptance.

The data collected by METICOS:

The data to be collected will not contain any personal or sensitive information that can identify you. Any personal information (eg. Name, contact details etc) that may be collected from you is for our internal processing and administrative purposes only, and to enable to contact you if we require further information.

AND/OR**PILOTS****Nature of participation:**

You will be asked to participate in METICOS pilot that will take place at [place] on [time]. During the pilots you will be asked to use the available equipment in your capacity as a [border control officer OR traveller].

You will be asked to provide your feedback and input on the efficiency and acceptance of such equipment by completing a questionnaire.

If you agree to take part to this activity, any personal information (eg. Name, contact details etc) that may be collected from you is for our internal processing and administrative purposes only, and to enable to contact you if we require further information.

The data collected during the METICOS pilots:

Two categories of data are being processed by the METICOS platform: primary and secondary data. Primary data are collected directly from participants whereas secondary data consist into statistical data as well as public data being further processed for the purpose of the METICOS platform.

More precisely:

- Primary data consist into the personal data collected via questionnaires, the METICOS Mobile Application and the METICOS Tablet application. The categories of data concerned are: time to cross the border, demographics & profile, smiley face, structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes (including questions regarding speed (queue, waiting time ?), accuracy, efficiency, user friendliness, data protection, privacy, ethical perception of traveler for the specific technology (and potentially generally). Moreover, some examples of questions may include: What are the main problems when crossing the border in general and have the SBC managed to resolve some? Which type of biometrics are you more in favour of? What kind of difficulties you encounter when using SBC? How important do you think speed/privacy/data protection/security/trustworthiness is in the context of SBC implementation? Was there sufficient and efficient communication signs? Any impact on personal health/wellbeing? Was there the adequate guidance needed?) and unstructured data in form of free text questions (Some examples of questions asked may include: In your opinion, the advantages of SBC outweigh the disadvantages and why? What problems have you encountered while using SBC technologies? Give a short review of your experience with SBC today. What did you like/not like?). In

addition, the METICOS platform may process tweets posted by the participant after crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, a using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag.

- Secondary data consist into:
 - Public tweets (or other public social media) collected for a long period of time which concern the public and societal acceptance of border control technologies. The METICOS platform downloads any related tweets periodically. The data retrieved are the date and time the tweet has been posted, the tweet's text, the tweet ID, number of retweets and likes, and the tweet's location. All other information is discarded. The aim is to process the tweet's text and derive the overall sentiment of the tweets, their geographic distribution and the context of discussion (most popular hashtags and mentions, topics people are tweeting about, entities identified in text, such as people, locations, organizations etc.). After having retrieved the above information, the tweets are deleted. The only information being kept is the aggregated results from the analysis performed above (sentiment, context of discussion, geographic distribution).
 - Online reviews which concern specific BCPs (airports/ports/land borders) published on websites and blogs.
 - Statistical and anonymized data originating from the border crossing points' databases.]

Your rights

During the trials, any participant who wishes to not to continue the trials will have the right to do so, without having to give explanations and without being affected in any way.

A participant may not be able to exercise their rights of access, rectification or erasure of his/her data as no data that could be used to identify that person will be collected. To exercise such rights, the participant may be required to provide additional information to enable his/her identification from the data collected by the METICOS joint controllers.

Contacts for further information and complaint

If you have any further question, you can contact any member of the METICOS research team. Moreover, to file a formal complaint, please contact any of the METICOS team representatives below:

1. Project coordinator

- Pantelis Velanas (may be contacted at P.Velanas@research.euc.ac.cy)

2. Project data protection responsible partner:

- Vrije Universiteit Brussel (may be contacted at franck.dumortier@vub.be)

3. Contact details of [Data Protection Officer of the activity's responsible partner]:

- [name, organisation name (may by contacted at [email])]

You also have the right to lodge a complaint with your data protection authority.

Thank you for taking part in the METICOS research.

Yours sincerely,

METICOS team

Informed consent form for participation in research

METICOS informed consent template

Project Title:

METICOS: A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

I, undersigned

[name]

[date of birth]

hereby give my consent to take part in the research carried out by the METICOS Research Consortium under the following conditions (**please tick box as appropriate**):

1. I have been informed that the METICOS (A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Control Technology) is a Research & Innovation Action No. {883075} to be run under the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (Topic SU-BES01-2019). The coordinator of the Research and Innovation Action is European University of Cyprus (Diogenis Str 6 Nicosia CY, 2404, Cyprus), represented by Dr. Pantelis Velanas).
2. I confirm that I am an adult (over 18 years old).
3. I have been informed about the purposes of the project, the activities to which I am involved and the purposes of my involvement to those activities.
4. I have been informed of the details of the research activity I will be participating.
5. I have had all my questions answered to my satisfaction.
6. I have been informed that I can also address any ethical questions or concerns arising from this research by means of contacting the coordinator.

7. My participation in the research will include the processing of personal data as described in the Information Sheet.
8. I understand that my data will be made available only to the members of the METICOS Research Consortium and to the European Commission.
9. I understand that any further use of this information will require my separate consent.
10. In the event of incidental findings I understand that such findings will be communicated to the Project Coordinator and Ethics Manager of METICOS and to the European Commission and will be handled in accordance with applicable legislation. I consent that I do not wish to receive information on the occurrence of such incidental findings.
11. I understand [I will / I will not] be paid for my participation.
12. I participate in this research activity voluntarily.
13. I give this consent fully informed, freely and voluntarily.
14. I understand that it is not feasible for me to exercise my rights to access, rectification or erasure of my data in the event that it is not possible to identify me from the data collected by the METICOS joint controllers unless I can provide additional information enabling my identification.
15. I hereby, agree to give personalized permission to METICOS to collect and process my personal data as provided in the Information Sheet and in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation.

Participant: _____

Name of Participant

Signature

Date

METICOS team representative:

Name of representative

Signature

Date